

PERCEPTIONS

UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT OF NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES, SOCIAL MEDIA, AND PERCEPTIONS IN COUNTRIES ABROAD ON MIGRATION FLOWS AND THE SECURITY OF THE EU & PROVIDE VALIDATED COUNTER APPROACHES, TOOLS AND PRACTICES

D2.5 Good practice collection

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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present in a structured manner the existing practices, measures, tools, models, and strategies for (counter-)acting on threats and expectations caused by a mismatch of expectation and reality due to different narratives on behalf of migrants, as provided by partners across the Consortium. To collect the good practices, both a direct and an indirect approach on addressing or counteracting issues resulting from a mismatch of expectation and reality was followed. There are several examples from the collected entries which have no direct link with false narratives, although the proposed countermeasure affects, among others, the perception that migrants have about Europe.

This collection of good practices provided the opportunity to experience and deeply understand several possible solutions and approaches that have or could be implemented to tackle effectively the issue of wrong expectations and narratives, which influence migration aspirations that may lead to several problems related to the migrant and/or the country of destination or even security threats and risks. It also showcased that a good practice may address a threat which was accurately perceived by migrants and refugees; the majority of good practices was dedicated to address a specific threat posed either to host countries/border security or to migrants themselves.

Their collection and initial presentation are intended to serve as a basis for the forthcoming Best Practice Library, which will entail all the selected identified best practices to be implemented into PERCEPTIONS web platform. Also, this deliverable will include the countermeasures along with lessons learnt to combat or counter-act on the existing threats or expectations that might be caused due to narratives and to be implemented into PERCEPTIONS toolkits.

The structure of the document is as follows: the first Chapter consists of introductory remarks, including a brief definition of a 'good practice'; then, the methodological approach is explained; thirdly, the collected data categories and trends are demonstrated in the form of statistics; moving on, the best practices identified through the collection of the material are mentioned and categorised; finally, conclusions from the initial data collection are drawn to be used for the creation of the best practice library to be incorporated into the PERCEPTIONS platform.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
AMIF	Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund
APP	Application
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DG CONNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DG Home	Directorate General for Migration and Home Affairs
EAVI	European Association for Viewers Interests
EC	European Council
ECRI	European Commission Against Racism and Intolerance
EFJ	European Federation of Journalists
EMN	European Migration Network
EU	European Union
EUROSUR	European Border Surveillance system
EWSI	European Web Site on Integration
FAG	Frequently Asked Questions
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IOM	International Organisation of Migration
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IRC	International Rescue Committee
LEA(s)	Law Enforcement Agencies
MENA	Middle East, North Africa
MRCC	Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre
MS	Member State
NCC	National Coordination Centre
NCCPIM&TIP	National Coordinating Committee on Combatting and Preventing Illegal Migration and Trafficking in Persons
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
ODIHR	Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights
OSCE	Organisation for Security and Co-operation in Europe
RAN	Radicalisation Awareness Network
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SAR	Search And Rescue
SFA	Swedish Forestry Agency
SNA	Social Network Analysis
SNCU	Swedish Nature Conservation Unit

SPES	Swedish Public Employment Service
TCN	Third Country National
UCFS	University of Cyprus Centre for Field Studies
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNHRC	United Nations Human Rights Council
UNSDG	UN Sustainable Development Group
UNU-MERIT	United Nations University-Maastricht Economic and Social Research Institute on Innovation and Technology
UTSS	Union Tunisienne de Solidarité Sociale
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The definition and semantic range of a ‘good practice’ or ‘best practice’ varies depending on the actors competent for its implementation, the objectives of the actors or for which the practice itself is implemented or suggested, the target groups of such practice and the broader context. The present document identifies good practices to be implemented mainly by governmental bodies, policymakers, legislators, civil society organisations and Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), and migrants, asylum-seekers, and refugees.

For the purposes of this deliverable, collection, ‘good practices’ have been defined as those practices, measures, tools and strategies for (counter-)acting on threats caused by narratives or perceptions and ‘misperceptions’ of migrants about Europe, taking in mind that ‘misperceptions’ is always a matter of perspective¹. However, as it has been discussed within the Consortium the content will be much dependent upon the findings of the partners and shall be formed all along the process of collection, categorisation, and analysis of the respective data.

Moreover, the Consortium decided that the definition can be open-ended and customised based on different approaches, including those related to best practices for addressing challenges regarding the safety and integrity of migrants and refugees and those related to threats to the security of the host country.

In the present document, we draw inspiration for filtering out and defining a measure, tool, practice, strategy as a ‘best practice’, among others, from the criteria used for identifying best practices that address challenges for the integration of migrants, refugees and asylum seekers. One example of this approach is that of the research team at the United Nations University-Maastricht Economic and Social Research Institute on Innovation and Technology (UNU-MERIT) and its School of Governance, in collaboration with the Hague Process on Refugees and Migration, which were based on the based the Cities of Migration methodology (Cities of Migration, 2020) and the International Labour Organisation criteria to define a ‘good practice’ for the purpose of the integration of migrants, refugees and asylum seekers as including the following six characteristics: practicality, innovation, successfulness, transferability, sustainability and strategic fit (Juzwiak et al., 2014). The criterion of ‘practicality’ presupposes the practical nature of an initiative, which shall address an integration need of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers but also that of other city residents (Juzwiak et al., 2014). ‘Innovation’

¹ For the purpose of this analysis, ‘migrants’ perceptions about a destination area’ (either of Europe or of a particular country) refers to the ideas and information (in the sense of knowledge) migrants have about the EU or about that country. Unlike the EUMAGINE approach, where impact of discourses on perceptions considered two types of ‘imaginings’ – the migratory project which refers to the ‘range of desired and desirable identities and lifestyles through which potential migrants imagine themselves’ and the geographical imaginings –, for the purpose of this analysis we will refer to geographical imaginings only. We employ a similar understanding of the concept, according to which ‘geographical imaginings’ refers to the subjectivity of the human conception of locations, spaces, countries and the people inhabiting these physical spaces (based on deliverable D2.3)

In subsequent consortium discussions, it was specified that ‘ideas and information’ as humanly experienced are always more than the sum of their referential components: they also carry affective charges and all the other experiential connotations that accompany human embodiment. Which is to say, within the project materials, ‘perceptions of [place]’ shall refer very broadly to ideas that embodied human subjects hold about that place. (based on deliverable D3.1)

requires that a good practice is creative in its approach, its resource utilisation, and collaboration methods to achieve its objectives (Juzwiak et al., 2014). The 'successfulness' of an integration practice reflects the positive effect it has on the migrant community and the city of residence. Such successfulness is not easily measured; however, the affected communities can be consulted and provide input on the issue, in order to estimate the practice's positive or negative impact (Juzwiak et al., 2014). The 'transferability' of a good practice is understood as its capability of being applicable in other contexts or areas of action. The 'sustainability' criterion is explained as a long-term assessment of migrants needs and context changes. Lastly, the 'strategic fit' means that an integration initiative shall be designed considering its application framework and context (Juzwiak et al., 2014).

A similar approach which was considered in this deliverable, is that of the good practices for the support of migrants, refugees and asylum seekers as described in PandPAS project (Mateus and Pinho, 2018). A good practice is characterised by: technical feasibility, efficacy and success, respect of the human rights and equity framework, replicability and adaptability, inherent participation, network coordination, gender sensitiveness, innovation, awareness, education, employment, entrepreneurship, governance, housing and settlement, political and public participation, social network and welcoming (Mateus and Pinho, 2018). The project also refers to the UNHRC Good Practices for Urban Refugees platform definition of a good practice as 'a process or methodology that is ethical, fair, and replicable, has been shown to work well, succeeds in achieving its objective(s), and therefore can be recommended as a model', which 'need not be viewed as prescriptive, but can be adapted to meet new challenges, becoming better as improvements are discovered.' (Mateus and Pinho, 2018).

In order to have a comprehensive understanding of a 'best practice', its definition in the security domain, and specifically that of border surveillance, which is closely related to the movement of migrants, refugees and asylum-seekers, is furthermore explored. These technical and operational guidelines, recommendations and best practices, including on cooperation with third countries, are mainly associated with the implementation and management of the European Border Surveillance System established by Regulation No 1052/2013 and are part of the EUROSUR Handbook which the Commission published in 2015. Indicatively, 'best practices' include, among others, the reinforcement of surveillance measures, the appropriate exchange of information among countries respecting the non-refoulement principle, but also physical and procedural reaction capability planning to sudden threats and illegal activities. Such 'best practices' cover 'reaction capability planning' the following border sections: : the terrain, geopolitical and environmental conditions of the external border and risk analysis overview; availability of resources in national , neighbouring Member State(s) and neighbouring third countries authorities for border surveillance and supporting authorities (human and technical resources, location, quantity, response time, communication channels); rules of engagement on jointly agreed reaction to different scenarios; and provisions regarding the mechanisms to protect fundamental rights, including international protection and the protection of vulnerable groups in case of mass arrivals (European Commission 2015a). In order to ensure the protection and saving the lives of migrants at sea, the 'best practices' include the timely establishment of communication channels between the National Coordination Centre (NCC) and the Maritime Rescue Coordination Centre (MRCC), the conclusion of a formal agreement for the exchange of information among them. Also, the patrol assets used for border surveillance operations should be equipped for search and rescue (SAR) operations (European Commission 2015a).

The contribution of partners from the Consortium in the collection of good practices resulted in the composition of an initial list of practices, while their typification as 'good practices' is to be identified and is subject to certain limitations. Firstly, there are many cases, in which information on the monitoring, measuring, evaluation and implementation obstacles of such practices, is lacking, rendering indefinite their characterisation as efficient. Also, it is prone to subjectivity, as what is considered a 'good' practice most likely would vary depending on the organisation or entity assessing the measure. Governmental authorities competent for the implementation of border security policies on the control of irregular migration are likely to assess certain countermeasures differently than a migrant or civil society organisations; and vice versa. So, when referring to 'good practices', it is important to have clear indicators about what is considered 'good' and why, and by whom.

In any case, a combination of the aforementioned definitions and criteria set by the migrant and refugee integration but also border security approach were used to guide the data collection and also serve as indicators of characterising a practice as 'good' / 'best'.

Lastly, the list of good practices should not be considered exhaustive. There may be more ad hoc activities like trainings and workshops or small-scale projects that are untraceable or not identified at this point of the research. Therefore, the focus of this deliverable is to indicatively list 'practices' that are applied in at the national, regional and international level as a response to threats in the migration context and elaborate on their key elements; it is not an exhaustive list of 'good practices' but can inspire the creation of best practices for the future.

2 Methodological Approach

This following section presents the methodology followed, as part of Work Package 2 (WP2 – RESEARCH: Literature, studies, projects, stakeholders, solutions, tools and practices), to collect, select and analyse the received data which will be further outlined in the next sections of this report.

2.1 Aim and Objectives

The aim of the collection of best practices is part of the objectives for WP2 laying out the theoretical scientific background for the project, investigating the state-of-the-art knowledge in the fields of border security, narratives on Europe, migration, European identity, and others. An overview of stakeholders, narratives, policies and legal frameworks, threats and risks has been conducted under T2.1, T2.2, T2.3, T2.4, respectively, and is completed with the overview of existing measures, tools, (counter-) acts and best practices under T2.5. The task is oriented to Objective #1 of PERCEPTIONS, which is to RESEARCH the body of scientific literature on the creation and distribution of narratives but also on relevant project outcomes, measures, and models.

More specifically, the main objective of the good practice collection report is to present the results of the initial assortment of best practices in a structured and comprehensive collection, thus creating the basis for the best practice library that will be implemented as part of PERCEPTIONS web platform. This will also provide the necessary knowledge for research to be conducted under WP3 and WP4. The best practice library will be used for the creation of a database to be transferred in interactive toolkits for the respective stakeholders, under WP5 and will be further deployed in the web platform of WP6 which will be evaluated under WP7.

The data was collected in order to identify pre-existent efficient practices of responding to threats related to perceptions or misperceptions of Europe by migrants, applied across several countries, which, after careful selection, categorisation, analysis, review and consolidation could compose a compendium or a digest for future influences or transplants in the migration and refugee context by the respective competent for implementation bodies. It must be noticed that selected good practices regarding the confrontation of threats related to narratives of the public opinion towards migrants were also included, to a limited extent, as a point of reference for future use and for reversed good practices.

2.2 Guidelines, Process, Criteria

All Consortium Partners engaged in T2.5 were sent the guide titled: “Guidance for WP2 Data Collection and Explanations of Templates”², accompanied by an excel template with the following categories:

- i. Origin of Source³
- ii. Type of proposed countermeasure⁴

² This guide can be found in Appendix A of the Deliverable D2.2. Secondary analysis of studies, projects, and narratives

³ The options provided were: **International, European, Regional, National, Other**

⁴ The partners have been give some indicative choices under which they could categorize the good practices they would come across, as follows: **Change on Legislation, Review of existing integration**

- iii. Year of Release
- iv. Name of the Organisation/ Institution/Entity proposing the countermeasure
- v. Level of the Organisation / Institution/Entity proposing the countermeasure⁴
- vi. Type of the Organisation / Institution/Entity proposing the countermeasure⁵
- vii. Level of the Organisation / Institution/Entity implementing the countermeasure⁴
- viii. Type of the Organisation / Institution/Entity implementing the countermeasure⁶
- ix. Detailed description of Countermeasure (including the threat background and the link with perceptions/false narratives)
- x. Populations which will be affected by the counter measure (e.g. Migrants, Refugees, Society in General etc.)
- xi. Duration of the proposed countermeasure
- xii. Implementation strategies of the proposed countermeasure
- xiii. Monitoring measures foreseen during the implementation phase of the proposed countermeasure
- xiv. Obstacles and other problems during the implementation phase
- xv. Existence of Evaluation Scheme⁶
- xvi. Description of evaluation Scheme
- xvii. Measurement of effectiveness/success of the proposed countermeasure (1-5 scale)⁷
- xviii. Weblink to the report/document etc.
- xix. Comments

Partners were provided with general instructions around the aim and objective of their research, the country division, the year of the identified sources as well as some proposed words that could use as search criteria, such as: *Migration, Migrant, False narratives, Origin country, Myths, Misperceptions, False Information, Practices, Countermeasures*. Partners could use those terms in a free form search so as to identify potential sources, not only in the English language, but also in their native language, under the premise that they can provide a well-rounded and detailed description of the Countermeasure in English.

More specific guidelines were not provided mainly because exploring existing practices, measures, tools, models, and strategies for (counter-)acting on threats and expectations caused by a mismatch of reality and expectation on behalf of migrants is a relevant new field. As such, in order to avoid limited responses, partners were free to include all their initial discoveries and then delve into more that will be presented in WP5 and the Library of Good Practice collection.

policies/procedures, Design of new integration policies/procedures, Info days/Training sessions to the relevant stakeholders (LEAs, Border control agencies, NGOs, General public, Public agencies), Info days/Training sessions to the migrants, Review of social media and other online platforms with up-to-date info on cultural, social, security, economic, political etc. info/country. There was also the **Other option** available in case they could not fit their findings to any of the proposed categories. These categories were influenced from a similar study conducted within the MigrEmpower project (MigrEmpower, 2019).

⁵ The options provided were: **Academic/Think Tank, Governmental/Polycymaking Body, Security/LEA/Border Agency, Civil Society / NGOs, Private Sector, Legal body, Other**

⁶ Partners were provided with the following options: Yes, No, Do not Know/Not Applicable

⁷ The 5-scale applied to this measurement was: 1-Very low, 2-Low, 3-Medium, 4-High and 5-Very high, in terms of effectiveness.

2.2.1 Countries covered in the analysis

The different types of organisations/partners that conducted the research in the countries mentioned previously and their experience on social research, minimised the possible bias on the final reporting and selection and report of the data. The countries that have been covered in this report are Algeria, Egypt, Tunisia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Spain, Morocco, Bulgaria, Kosovo, Germany, and UK. These countries had been initially selected based on their classification (IOM, 2018) as Countries of Origin⁸ (Algeria, Egypt, Tunisia, Morocco), Host/Destination countries⁹ (Greece, Cyprus, Italy, Spain, Germany) and Transit countries¹⁰ (Bulgaria, Kosovo). Due to the fact that many countries initially identified as countries of origin, can also be considered host and/or transit countries for migrants from other countries,¹¹ it is highlighted that this initial categorisation was tailored for the purposes of PERCEPTIONS. Participants have not restricted their research to only their countries, but they have also included any relevant documents from international and EU level. Partners from Austria have included several practices both on national and EU levels.

The total collection period lasted for three months (October – December 2019), with no upper or lower limits per partner (each partner could add and send as many entries as they could find). The final datasets were submitted to KEMEA, as Task leader of 2.5, who also made some additions until the end of February 2020.

2.2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

The following table identifies all the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to the collected entries in order to establish the final dataset for analysis.

Table 1. List of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<p>Practices, measures, tools, models, and strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ that are relevant to best practices on migration, narratives, and the EU. ✓ that have been issued after 2015¹². ✓ from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic resources (peer-reviewed journals, academic books, conference proceedings and dissertations) 	<p>Practices, measures, tools, models, and strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ with no focus on the subject we are addressing ✗ when they are published before 2015 ✗ when they address the same outcome (only the most recent will be included) ✗ with no available detailed abstract in English

⁸ According to International Organization of Migration (IOM, 2020a), “In the migration context, a country of origin is a country of nationality or of former habitual residence of a person or group of persons who have migrated abroad, irrespective of whether they migrate regularly or irregularly”

⁹ According to IOM (IOM 2020), “In the migration context, a country of destination is a country that is the destination for a person or a group of persons, irrespective of whether they migrate regularly or irregularly”

¹⁰ According to IOM (IOM, 2020), “in the migration context, the country of transit is the country through a person, or a group of persons pass on any journey to the country of origin or the country of habitual residence”

¹¹ As a matter of fact, Algeria, Egypt, Tunisia, and Morocco can be also classified as transit/host countries. This is because they receive migrants from neighbouring countries that either stay there for ever or for a while trying to reach Europe.

¹² The year 2015 has been used as a milestone that indicates the start of the Migration Crisis in Europe and more in particular the unprecedented influx of refugees and migrants, as more than 1 million people arrived in the European Union, most of them fleeing from war and terror in Syria and other countries (European Commission, 2017).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Popular resources (magazine and newspaper articles, press stories, websites, social media accounts and wikis) - Other similar projects on migration narratives and perceptions, including those funded from the EU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grey literature produced by international and EU organisations, governmental and policymaking bodies, NGOs, and civil society organisations, think tanks, lobbies, legal bodies, security, LEAs, border agencies, and the private sector - Other Electronic databases ✓ written in one the following languages: English, French, Italian, German, Greek, or with a detailed abstract in English ✓ publicly available material or made public via agreement of a classified IPR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ when the full text is not freely accessible ✗ from sources that are not complied with GDPR
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2.3 Final dataset

Following the collection period, the final number of entries in the database received from the PERCEPTIONS Consortium partners were $N_0=207$. Having already set the inclusion and exclusion criteria, all the entries were assessed according to their eligibility. According to Figure 1, at first all the entries published before 2015 ($N_1=24$) have been excluded. Then the remaining entries ($N_2=183$) have been rescreened using a thorough full text analysis. The duplicates as well as the non-relevant entries ($N_2=34$) have been cleared, leading to a remaining dataset of $N=149$ entries.

Figure 1. Process of selecting the final dataset for D2.5

3 Descriptive Analysis of the Dataset

Certain descriptive analysis has been applied to the final dataset, so as to have a better understanding of the collected data. To begin with, it should be highlighted that due to the timing of the data collection (up to February 2020), the development in 2020 of the volume of proposed practices is still to be determined. Of course, during the activities in task T5.3 of WP5, the dataset will be update and further enhanced with new entries, so as to present a well-rounded library of good practices.

The majority of the proposed practices, measures and strategies have been clustered around the years 2017, 2018 and 2019 (Figure 2). This can be explained by the fact that since the beginning of the so-called ‘migration crisis’, this phenomenon has been acknowledged as an issue that requires a global approach and coordinated responses on an international level. It has not been tackled only on a country-by-country level, but also through a regional, European, and International perspective, with all the interested stakeholders (governmental bodies, NGOs and civil society organisations, public authorities, LEAs and border control agencies, the general public and migrants themselves) to seek and propose different measures and strategies.

Figure 2. Year of release of the proposed Practice/Measure/Tool/Strategy

Almost 2 out of 10 organisations proposed information days and training to other stakeholders (LEAs, border authorities, the general public etc.) as counter-strategy, with both the organisation/planning of information days and training to migrants for awareness raising around multiple issues, as well as the design of new integration procedures (Figure 3), to follow with a percentage of 16% respectively. In addition to that, 25% of the entries present strategies/tools and measures that have been proposed through funded projects (EU, regional and national), while 4 out of 10 organisations also included the incorporation and adoption of new technologies, such as e-learning platforms, mobile applications, websites and art based campaigns as an innovative tool for migrant integration in the local society (McAuliffe, 2016) as well as in addressing potential threats against migrant and/or refugees, either during their journeys or inside the destination country (Szczepanikova and Van Criekeing, 2018). Finally, combined practices falling under the majority of 34% namely “other” section included several

sub-strategies such as: (social) media awareness campaigns against migrant smuggling, human trafficking and radicalisation, toolkits and other informational/training material against misinformation around migrants and refugees, review reports, campaigns and other publications around public perceptions towards migrants not only on an international and EU level but also on national level (e.g. Greece, Cyprus, Germany etc.), reports and interventions on migrant integration and reintegration, as well as story sharing platforms and art-driven projects (cinema, photography, theatre) aiming to raise awareness to migrants against irregular migration and on the real depiction of Europe to their nationals.

Figure 3. Type of proposed Practice/Measure/Tool/Strategy

Moving on to the type of the organisation proposing certain measures/tools/practices/strategies, Table 2 presents the interrelation of the former with the level of organisation that will or supposed to implement them. As illustrated more than half of the organisations were Civil Society/NGOs (51% of the total sample), followed by the Governmental/Policy-making bodies (34.8%).

Table 2. Interrelation between Type of organisation proposing and Level of organisation

Level of Organisation (implementation level)	Type of Organisation (proposal level)						Frequencies
	Academic Think Tank	Civil Society NGOs	Governmental Policy-making Body	Private Sector	Security LEA Border Agency	Other	
European	2	12	13	1	0	0	28
International	1	18	13	0	0	0	32
National	5	39	25	3	2	6	80
Regional	1	7	1	0	0	0	9
Frequencies	9	76	52	4	2	6	149

This can be explained by the fact that a lot of entries stemmed from past or current funded programs, including info days and training sessions as well as policies and procedures, mostly performed by the previously mentioned types of actors (European website on Integration, 2020). In addition to this, organisations on a national level are more frequent than the rest to implement the proposed strategies (53.7% of the total sample) followed by those on an International (21.5%) and European (18.8%) level.

Figure 4 provides insight into the relationship between the types of measures proposed and the type of organisation proposing these measures, highlighting once more the dominance of Civil society/NGOs along with Governmental Policy making bodies in all the measure/practices categories.

Figure 4. Frequencies of type of measures per type of organisation proposing these measures

When evaluating monitoring measures, 88% of the entries have reported that for the reported practices there were no certain monitoring measures, or they are unknown/unpublished even if they do exist. Only 22 out of 149 entries reported the existence of a certain evaluation scheme for the proposed measure, reporting different impact indicators, such as the number of people who benefit from the certain measure, the migrant integration impact level, the number of sessions and campaigns organised for certain initiatives, as well as the outcomes of questionnaires, feedback and official reports. The number of entries indicating the effectiveness level each practice presented is even lower, with only 16 entries to have included the relevant impact scale. The low response level to these indicators is aligned with the findings in deliverable *D2.2 Secondary analysis of studies, projects, and narratives*, which highlighted the limited literature that looks at the impact of countermeasures on changing the perceptions and expectations of migrants. This situation underlines the importance in the upcoming document of Best Practice Library in WP5, to develop a template with specific question

on the way each measure had been ‘innovative, developing creative solutions; showing a positive impact on the level of implementation of the human rights of migrants; having a sustainable effect, especially by involving migrants themselves; and having the potential for replication’, according to the definition of Best Practice by IOM (IOM,2011).

Before moving to the initial analysis of the identified practices and their links to current threats, as described in deliverable *D2.4 Collection of threats and security issues*, it is important to highlight three crucial facts. Firstly, it is worth indicating that according to the reporting there has been an overall satisfying level of countries where each of the relevant strategies have or are going to be implemented on a national level (Figure 5). However, a lot of partners have included in their reporting several strategies and measures which stretch across an international and EU levels.

Figure 5. Frequency of Countries implementing the proposed measures at a national level

Secondly, the target groups of the people who could benefit from each best practices seems unified under the umbrella of the terms ‘migrant’¹³ and ‘refugee’¹⁴; however, there are diversifications on practices that target also specifically refugees, asylum seekers, female migrants, minors, labour migrants, other vulnerable groups of migrants and/or returnees. In addition to this, a large proportion

¹³ According to IOM, ‘migrant is an umbrella term, not defined under international law, reflecting the common lay understanding of a person who moves away from his or her place of usual residence, whether within a country or across an international border, temporarily or permanently, and for a variety of reasons’ (IOM, 2020a)

¹⁴ According to IOM, a refugee is ‘A person who qualifies for the protection of the United Nations provided by the High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), in accordance with UNHCR’s Statute and, notably, subsequent General Assembly’s resolutions clarifying the scope of UNHCR’s competency, regardless of whether or not he or she is in a country that is a party to the 1951 Convention or the 1967 Protocol – or a relevant regional refugee instrument – or whether or not he or she has been recognized by his or her host country as a refugee under either of these instruments’ (IOM, 2020a)

of the good practices (46.6% of the total sample) also target other stakeholders, such as public bodies, the general public and society as a whole.

Finally, as it has been previously mentioned in the introductory section, even though the scope of this deliverable is to initially capture and present in a structured manner the existing practices, measures, tools, models and strategies for (counter-)acting on threats and expectations caused by a mismatch of expectation and reality due to narratives on behalf of migrants, several entries have also captured measures and strategies addressing certain behaviours (e.g. public perceptions on migrants and refugees), which were classified as indirect ways of addressing the abovementioned phenomena.

4 Good Practices, Measures, Tools identified in the dataset

As it mentioned previously, this deliverable has as its main objective to present an initial collection and analysis of existing practices, measures, tools, models and strategies for tackling on threats and expectations caused by false narratives on behalf of migrants for the destination countries or Europe in general. This document is also aligned with the threat analysis which was carried out as part of the literature review completed in task *T2.2 Accumulate studies, project reports, and relevant secondary data about migration and narratives within the EU and partner countries* and reported in deliverable *D2.2 Secondary analysis of studies, projects, and narratives*. Secondary analysis of studies, projects, and narratives as well as in the deliverable *D2.4 Collection of threats and security issues*, the following section presents the collected good practices, measures and tools classified under six main categories:

1. Migrant integration in the host country (education, labour, housing, cultural integration)
2. Tackling radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and/or terrorism
3. Review of media representations of migrants and other fake news
4. Awareness raising on the migrant journey and the risks associated with irregular migration routes (human trafficking, migrant smuggling, deaths, etc.) along with policies to tackle them
5. Addressing negative public perceptions racism and xenophobia towards migrants in the host country
6. Protection of human rights of migrants and protection against other threats related to them in the host country (policies)

These categories can be directly and/or indirectly associated with the previously mentioned threats, as illustrated in Table 3, also indirectly contributing to the migration-relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) targets and indicators (1,3,4,5,8,10,11,13,16 and 17) (Migration Data Portal, 2020), which have as a main aim to ‘facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people, including through the implementation of planned and well-managed migration policies, to reduce inequality within and among countries, and address other migration related issues such as trafficking, remittances, international student mobility and more’.

Table 3. Association among reported good practices and identified threats

Good practices, measures, and tools	Associated Threats
Migrant integration in the host country (education, labour, housing, health, cultural integration)	5.1.3. Discrimination 5.1.7. Economic 5.1.8. Civil Unrest 5.1.9. Health Problems and Disease
Tacking radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and/or terrorism	5.1.3. Discrimination 5.1.5. Violent Radicalisation and Terrorism 5.1.12. Domestic Violent Extremism
Review of media representations of migrants and other fake news	5.1.3. Discrimination 5.1.5. Violent Radicalisation and Terrorism 5.1.7. Economic (including labour) 5.1.8. Civil Unrest 5.1.9. Health Problems and Disease

	<p>5.1.10. Human Smuggling and Trafficking/Modern Slavery</p> <p>5.1.11. Corruption</p> <p>5.1.12. Domestic Violent Extremism</p> <p>5.1.13. Environmental</p>
Awareness raising on the migrant journey and the risks associated with irregular migration routes (human trafficking, migrant smuggling, deaths, etc.) along with policies to tackle them	<p>5.1.1. Death</p> <p>5.1.4. Violence and Abuse</p> <p>5.1.10. Human Smuggling and Trafficking/Modern Slavery</p> <p>5.1.11. Corruption</p>
Addressing negative public perceptions racism and xenophobia towards migrants in the host country	<p>5.1.3 Discrimination</p> <p>5.1.5 Violent radicalisation and Terrorism</p> <p>5.1.6 Minor, Serious and Organised Crime</p> <p>5.1.7. Economic</p> <p>5.1.8. Civil Unrest</p> <p>5.1.9. Health Problems and Disease</p> <p>5.1.13. Environmental</p>
Protection against the violation of migrants' human rights and against other threats related to them in the host country (Policies)	<p>5.1.1. Death</p> <p>5.1.2. Detention and deportation</p> <p>5.1.3. Discrimination</p> <p>5.1.4. Violence and Abuse</p> <p>5.1.8 Civil Unrest</p> <p>5.1.9. Health Problems and Disease</p> <p>5.1.10 Human smuggling and Trafficking/Modern Slavery</p>

There is also a final general category which includes good practices and tools stemming primarily from migrant stories and address combined versions of the previously mentioned issues and threats (e.g. the depiction of Europe in countries of origin, issues around reintegration of migrants in their original countries, threats before, during and after the migrant journey, etc.). It was decided to use this final category, as the practices proposed could not adapt to only one of the prementioned categories.

The following subsections present an initial classification of the identified measures, practices and tools that have been reported by the consortium partners, also outlining their main points.

4.1 Migrant integration in the host country (education, labour, housing, health, and cultural integration)

Migrant integration has gained a crucial place in the global agenda and is addressed by the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda's call to 'leave no one behind' (UNSDG, 2019). The concept of integration is the 'two-way process of mutual adaptation between migrants and the societies in which they live, whereby migrants are incorporated into the social, economic, cultural and political life of the receiving community. It entails a set of joint responsibilities for migrants and communities and incorporates other related notions such as social inclusion and social cohesion' (IOM, 2020).

Integration can occur both on a private and public level, across generations, and at the individual, family, community, and national levels (Council of the European Union, 2004). Initiatives, practices, measures, and tools around migrant integration in the host countries can directly and/or indirectly enhance the perceptions migrants have for the latter. In particular, migrants can shape well-rounded narratives around each host country and Europe based on the integration procedures they encounter in each country as well as on the level of information they are able to access for each of the host countries. These narratives can also directly impact the truthfulness of the stories that migrants share among them for awareness raising and proper expectations setting before migrating to each country.

As a matter of fact, 35 out of the 149 entries are practices that address these kinds of issues. The majority of them have been released in 2017 (11 out of 35), with the year of 2019 to follow (10 out of 51). 60% of them have been proposed by civil society/NGOs, while the rest stemmed from governmental organisation and policy making bodies. The majority of them (68.5%) were implemented on a national level with the rest to be equally divided between European and international level of implementation. Fifteen (15) entries included certain technologies (e.g. e-learning platforms, digital tools, and interactive websites) as end-product of their implementation.

The following table (Table 4) summarizes the key findings of the dataset.

Table 4. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on Migrant integration in the host country

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
ICT, Interactive platforms, and digital tools, methodology and innovative techniques	Migrant integration (field of education)	VALUE is an Erasmus + project that equips and encourages schools to improve their educational processes through the use of multilingual practices. It provides teachers with methodologies, tools, and practices (innovative interactive teaching techniques, ICT, digital storytelling, open interactive platform) to include students of migrant background in their classes effectively and support them in being integrated into the school community.
Synthesis report	Migrant integration (field of labour)	This synthesis report has been produced by the European Migration Network (EMN), having as aim to inform the target audience (e.g. practitioners, policy officers, decisionmakers at both EU and national level including academic researchers and the general public, the Commission and the European Asylum Support Office) on the application of integration support measures for beneficiaries of international/humanitarian protection in relation to labour market access and participation, identifying existing policies and support measures.
Trainings, learning modules and online platform	Migrant integration (field of education)	Ecourse is an Erasmus + project that aims at enhancing the access, participation and learning performance of newly arrived migrants and refugee children in primary school education in

		Germany, Greece, Italy, France, and Cyprus as well as at a European level, through learning modules and a school support platform in order to promote their overall integration in the host societies.
Online learning platform	Migrant integration (field of education)	GVETS is an Erasmus + project that aims to develop an online learning platform (through gamification) for the improvement of skills and competences of professionals working with children in migration environments.
Training courses, online observatory, digital toolbox	Migrant integration (field civic and political participation)	ADmiRe (Adult Migrant Integration Experts) is an Erasmus + project that aims to develop the competencies of the adult education staff, migrant support staff and migrants addressing key gaps in terms of knowledge, skills and expertise in the fields of integration, networking, political socialisation and civic participation. Its main outcomes will be a digital Toolbox with Migrant Integration Resources, an Induction Training Course for adult educators as well as an online Observatory of Political Systems in Cyprus, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain.
Workshops, trainings, and e-learning platform	Migrant integration (use of new technologies and media in the field of labour, education, general participation)	MedLit - "Media literacy for refugee, asylum seeking and migrant women", is an Erasmus + project that contributes to the integration of migrant women in 6 EU member states, Austria, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta, and the UK by enhancing the media literacy competencies of migrant women to facilitate their integration as well as enabling them to access, interpret, use and produce information and other media content in a safe and responsible manner. Longer term, the objective is to allow women to use digital skills to look for a job, learning the language of the host country, access information about available services or political/administrative information, promote integration in the relevant networks. Association and other organisations working with migrants and refugees will also have access to new tools to improve the targeting and integration of refugees
Digital portfolio of personal information and important certificates and qualifications	Migrant integration of newly arrived migrants in the Rhein-Neckar district (Germany) (field of education and labour)	The online application MoBio (Mobile Biography) allows newly arrived migrants in the Rhein-Neckar district (Germany) to upload personal information and important certificates and qualifications. The information provided through the uploaded documents serve as the basis for drawing up integration plans and agreements on objectives. Its aim is to enable refugees to compile their own personal information as a

		digital portfolio in order to support their integration process in all areas of society. The software allows refugees to freely access their data and share them with relevant third parties. This can help avoid duplication of information or documents in different places. Furthermore, it enhances cooperation between the people and organisations involved in the integration process.
Collection of strategies (Housing and voluntary mentoring system, orientation courses, workshops and language classes, Labour market, Café International)	Integration of newly arrived migrants in the city of Altena (Germany) (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	Under the theme 'From refugee to citizen', the city of Altena, Germany has taken a whole-of-society approach to refugee integration, with civil society serving as the main actor. Altena has implemented numerous initiatives that help promote the integration of newcomers into the community. The city has supported civil society in implementing initiatives in a range of areas, including housing support, mentoring, language learning and labour market integration. Altena's approach has been praised in media reports and is often noted as a best practice and model for other European cities.
Collection of strategies (welcome folder, language courses, mentoring activities, welcome cafes)	Refugee integration in the city of Schneverdingen (Germany) (field of education, labour, health, housing)	The city of Schneverdingen, Germany has implemented a range of refugee integration initiatives, such as welcome cafés organised on a weekly basis, one-on-one meetings between aid workers and refugees, and various activities such as a reading group, cooking group, bicycle workshop, group for mothers. Following social orientation for refugees, the integration initiatives focus on the needs of people in their educational and professional lives. Relevant local institutions like the daycare centre, school, vocational school, and the Federal Employment Agency are also well prepared to handle the needs of refugees. An informational website and a variety of informational materials complement the initiatives.
Two training Manuals addressed to trainers and trainees	Migrant integration (field of education, labour, health, housing, civic and political participation, legislation issues)	The training manuals (for trainees and trainers) published by the Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights (ODIHR) of the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) is intended for use during training courses related to developing, implementing, and reviewing migrant integration policies in the OSCE region. The target audience for the training courses are government officials, members of parliament, representatives of national, regional, and local authorities, social partners, and civil society actors.

<p>Community of Practice (CoP) approach using also other methods such as: Circle Practice, World Café, Storytelling, drawing, Theatre etc.</p>	<p>Long term migrant integration processes in certain regions in Lower Austria (field of social integration and political participation)</p>	<p>The aim of the activities is to foster and build intercultural competencies, to make the multiple engagements of society visible and to provide a platform for sharing good-practices, and to teach tools and methods to empower for (political) processes in their own small municipalities, encourage for empowerment.</p>
<p>Upgraded Information Guide of Cyprus and mobile app.</p>	<p>Integration of newly arrived migrants in Cyprus (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)</p>	<p>The consulting firm INNOVADE, in collaboration with the international research center CARDET, received support to upgrade guide with general information about Cyprus. The Guide includes information about Cyprus, in an effort to help to the TCNs integration process, as well as to facilitate their integration, their employment, and their social integration, while benefiting the local community and economy. It is translated in the languages (English, Russian, Sri Lankans [Sinhala and Tamil], Arabic and Filipino). The guide is available through a mobile APP and in print</p>
<p>Intervention methodology that combines together training and direct learning moments through internship experiences</p>	<p>Integration of young refugees (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)</p>	<p>Casa Scalabrini 634, is a program of the Scalabrinian Agency for Development Cooperation (ASCS Onlus), which Implements an individualized path and job placement of the young refugees in the world of social agriculture.</p>
<p>Counselling and assistance services</p>	<p>Integration of migrants with a prospect of long-term residence status and adult refugees who suffer from psychological trauma (field of housing and psychologic assessment)</p>	<p>The Project 'Support in household Energy Efficiency' is funded by the City of Leipzig and functions as a coordination office for energy efficiency counselling for low-income households in Leipzig, particularly those housing refugees. In total, the activities that will be done throughout project's duration are migration counselling, psychosocial support, treatment, therapy, energy efficiency advice.</p>
<p>Report for preparatory action on behalf of cities for migration</p>	<p>Integration and social cohesion of migrants in the urban environment</p>	<p>This report from the World Economic Forum seeks to provide city leaders with long-term solutions, focusing on addressing urban infrastructure and services challenges – affordable and social housing, quality education and health services, robust and congestion-free roads and transportation infrastructure, simple access to basic utilities and social cohesion across communities. The report seeks to help cities prepare for these challenges with a roadmap for</p>

		city leaders to address them over the next decades, which can be accelerated by leveraging greater public private collaboration. In addition, we hope that this report will provide the forthcoming United Nations Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration, with a unique perspective on how migration is affecting cities around the world
Online medical directory	Protection of health of migrants in the Darmstadt-Dieburg district (Germany)	The Darmstadt-Dieburg district (Germany) has published a directory of doctors for migrants titled 'Which doctor speaks my language?' Medical practitioners in the district who speak languages in addition to German are listed in the publication, together with their areas of specialisation and details of their practice. This makes it easier for migrants in the area to obtain good health care.
Collective report	Integration of migrants in the host society (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	A collective report on strategies and recommendations on education of refugees/migrants programmes, host country language learning, integration to the labour market programmes, socio-cultural and psychological support programmes, financial support programmes, housing programmes, through several examples around Europe
Evaluation report and recommendations	Integration of migrants in the host society (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	Evaluation scheme and further recommendations on the UNHCR's response to the influx of refugees from Syria into Turkey
Collection and sharing of methodologies and stories on the website, as well as offering support to stakeholders interested in the method.	Integration of young and mostly unaccompanied migrants in Sicily, Puglia, and Calabria (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	This good practice, stemmed from Save the Children Onlus Italy, Authority for the protection of children and adolescents, and Interior Minister aims to promote and disseminate participatory best practices with migrant children arriving by sea, tested at the southern border within the Praesidium Project (Sicily, Puglia and Calabria). They concern the design and implementation of participatory pathways in the first reception places of unaccompanied foreign minors and within the communities for minors, with the following objectives: - social inclusion (enhancement of each child's personality - promotion of recognition and self-awareness); - decompression with respect to often difficult living conditions; - expression and enhancement of children's experiences and knowledge; - influence on decision-makers (to improve services, programs and policies for them). The methodology of participatory pathways allows

		them to be truly accessible (in terms of time, space, themes, results), flexible, relevant to the lives of migrants and consider the specificity of participants and their contexts of belonging and origin. It not only direct positive effects (on migrants) but also on the whole of civil society as regards the values of integration, social inclusion and respect for migrants, and their histories, on which the educational and assistance activities exposed are based.
Social networking, physical activities, and trainings	Integration of migrants in Sweden (field of education, health, civic local life)	The Nature Integration Program, resulted from a partnership between The Swedish Public Employment Service (SPES), the Swedish Forestry Agency (SFA) and the Swedish Nature Conservation Unit (SNCU), and addresses vocational and language skills for migrants, including social networking and physical activities, evaluating the use of nature and nature-based activities to help integrate migrants in Sweden and promote good health.
Handbook from the Bulgarian Red Cross	Integration of Persons who have been granted Asylum or International protection in Bulgarian Municipalities (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	The Handbook aims to provide municipalities, as well as all stakeholders, with the maximum amount of information and guidance required to foster and support the refugee integration process. A good integration environment can avoid the risk of extremism or of falling into human trafficking structures among migrant populations. As concluding activities of this initiative are integration agreements between municipalities, foreigners, and the SAR. These agreements will contain measures such as: providing of housing, Bulgarian courses, enrolment at a kindergarten or compulsory school for children, health insurance and services, professional orientation, inclusion, and training.
Delivery of services to migrants, collaboration schemes between migrant and refugee community organisations and mainstream service providers, including the legal and housing sectors,	Integration of migrants in the UK (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	Route to Your Rights (RTYR) project, is a qualitative research and advocacy project explored issues that push migrants into a more vulnerable state, like labour exploitation and homelessness during settlement in the UK, and in particular, how access to certain services and opportunities impact on their ability to build a flourishing life in UK. It also aims to pull out regional variations of migrants' experiences across London, Manchester, and Coventry, in addition to the impact of housing, employment and immigration issues on mental and physical health, and the gendered experience of migration. The identified issues include lack of

workshops, training, and campaigns		familiarity with the UK employment, housing and health system; high concentration of precarious employment contracts; poor housing and working conditions; structural barriers, such as restrictions on access to benefits and welfare support; language and cultural barriers; and limited capacity of support services are also key contributing factors to preventing a more positive settlement experience.
Book with specific recommendations	Integration of migrants in Spain (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	This book presents a compilation of articles for reflection and analysis on the migratory phenomenon in Spain and in the countries of origin and transit. It has an outstanding number of authors, all of them professionals from the media, national and international organisations and agencies, researchers, and university professors. The book compiles comments, recommendations, and prospects on the evolution of immigration, from full respect to the opinion and plurality of its authors.
Mobile Application	Integration of migrants in Italy (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)	The App I-Migr is part of the project "PINSEC - Young women and migrants: paths of social and economic inclusion in Tunisia", directed by, CIES onlus, co-financed by the Italian Agency for Development Cooperation. Involvements of other partners such as the Union Tunisienne de Solidarité Sociale - UTSS. "I-Migr" is the first mobile application in Tunisia that offers the opportunity know the main services offered to migrants, in the form of an electronic directory presented in a simplified way to guide different beneficiaries in order to guarantee them a better integration into society Tunisian. I-Migr application was launched with 10 categories of services: legal assistance, services for victims of trafficking or violence, medical assistance, psychological assistance, social assistance, economic integration, assistance at departure, assistance for the return to Tunisia, culture, and sport
Holding a series of events with a duration of two hours, with the assistance of an interpreter and a mediator: co-mixing bread for children from refugee and	Integration through cultural exchange of children (age 7-11 years) from refugee families and Bulgarian families	"We are all made of the same dough" project is designed to establish cultural exchange, lasting relationships, and communication between children of migrant background (refugees and asylum seekers) and children from Bulgarian society. The main objective of the project is to establish cultural exchange, lasting relationships, and communication between children of migrant background (refugees and asylum seekers) and children from Bulgarian society. The project aims

<p>Bulgarian families, united around different topics for each session (holidays, customs, national cuisine, seasons, home, family, friendships, traditions, etc.).</p>		<p>to educate children about both their commonalities and differences, and to help overcome them. The initiative addresses the need for integration and adaptation of refugee children and, at the same time, overcoming fears and prejudices in the local community.</p>
<p>Comparative analysis and recommendations</p>	<p>Integration of migrants in Greece (field of education, labour, health, housing, political and civic local life)</p>	<p>This comparative Analysis of the Integration of Immigrants and Refugees in Greece offers Optimal Practices, Policy Suggestions through the analysis of personal experiences from the beneficiaries. The main objectives of this research are to suggests optimal policies for the integration of migrants and refugees based on international experience and identify those practices that are most widely accepted by immigrants / refugees, shedding light on a parameter that has been overlooked by previous studies, that of the opinion of the immigrants / refugees themselves.</p>
<p>Buddy system and co-housing in innovative housing units</p>	<p>Integration of migrants in Belgium (field of education, housing, civic local life)</p>	<p>The Co-housing and case management for Unaccompanied young adult Refugees in ANTwerp CURANT-project proposes a mixed use of a set of policy instruments order to help young adult refugees. CURANT supports unaccompanied young adults between the ages of 17 and 22 years, who arrived in Belgium without their parents and who have been granted refugee status or subsidiary protection. When unaccompanied minors reach legal adulthood, they no longer are eligible for housing in reception centres, enrolment in reception classes in schools, customised training courses for minors and support from a legal guardian. One of the innovative aspects of CURANT concerns the involvement of young, Dutch-speaking locals, called 'buddies', in a cohousing setting. Buddies are volunteers between the ages of 20 and 31 years. After a screening and intake procedure, the refugees and buddies are matched and become flat mates. Both the buddies and the refugees receive substantial support in the framework of CURANT and pay an affordable rent (€250). With the buddying system, CURANT aims to develop informal learning processes, to make the social networks of the refugees and buddies more diverse and improve the Dutch language competencies of the refugees. A total of 75</p>

		<p>cohousing units will be set up through purchase, renovation, and private renting. In these units minimum 75 and maximum 135 unaccompanied young refugees cohabit with Flemish buddies for at least 1 year. The buddy helps the refugee with different aspects. For example: looking for a job, building a network, learning Dutch.</p>
<p>Urban Innovative Actions, Capacity building lab, neighbourhood activities and affordable housing models based on exchange systems</p>	<p>Integration of migrants in Athens (field of education, housing, civic local life)</p>	<p>The “Curing the Limbo” project capitalises on Athens’ vibrant civil society to help refugees and the local unemployed to overcome the stage of inertia. The programme develops around a circular “gift” system, addressing the twofold issue of both housing and inactivity: Refugees receive affordable living spaces from the city’s available housing stock and in return, they work for the public benefit, supporting the needs of the local community and participating in citizen-led activities that improve quality of life in Athenian neighbourhoods. Beneficiaries receive on-the-job training supervised by the University of Athens, which includes language learning, psychosocial support, “street law” knowledge and other basic social and soft skills. These skills are tailored to the beneficiaries’ needs and are offered in an integrated way, during which other parallel activities are also gradually introduced. The modality of exchange is developed around the incentives given both to tax-paying proprietors of currently empty spaces as well as to the beneficiaries through their integrated inclusion in the city.</p>
<p>Recommendations list</p>	<p>Integration of migrants in Cyprus (field of education, housing, health, employment political and civic local life)</p>	<p>The UNHCR UN agency in Cyprus provides a list of practical and meaningful ways (UNHCR Integration Recommendations) to ensure the effective integration of refugees whom the Republic of Cyprus has had the privilege to protect. Regarding unemployment, the UNHCR recommends the mapping of academic qualifications, skills, work experience of refugees to ensure a better job referral system, which currently lacks information of the profiles of refugees residing in Cyprus. In addition, language programs are implemented through NGOs, volunteer groups and local authorities and have lacked continuity and tended to have high dropout rates. The UNHCR has recommended promoting language and job-readiness simultaneously by offering vocational training linked with language instruction, which is both cost effective and more motivating for refugees.</p>

<p>Language advice program</p>	<p>Language counselling as a part of labour market integration in Germany</p>	<p>Since 2005, the Darmstadt-Dieburg district (Germany) has had a central ‘language advice’ unit within the municipal job centre, under the authority responsible for labour market integration. Staff trained in German as a second language offer support in applying for language courses and reimbursement of expenses, in addition to initial consultation and individual advice on suitable types of courses. The language advice process is directly tied in with the overall process of labour market integration and goes hand-in-hand with the work of staff in case management. The work of the language advice unit is directly tied into the process of labour market integration. Case managers who monitor the process of labour market integration, but who do not necessarily have expert knowledge in the area of learning a second language, can make appointments for their clients with the language advice unit. Staff of the language advice unit conduct a detailed assessment of the language level and pace of learning of the person concerned, their geographical mobility and time flexibility. In agreement with case managers, the unit provides support in choosing a suitable course, registering for it, and applying for reimbursement of the costs.</p>
<p>Book chests made up of a selection of multilingual children’s books and CDs.</p>	<p>Integration of migrant children in Germany (field of education, and language)</p>	<p>Under the motto ‘Multilingualism in families – multilingualism is a treasure’, the Office for Migration and Inclusion of the Municipality of Darmstadt-Dieburg (Germany) has put together ‘book chests’ made up of a selection of multilingual children’s books and CDs. Educational establishments in the district can borrow these materials for their work in looking after and educating children. In addition to books and CDs, the chests contain informational brochures and materials for teachers, as well as information for parents in various languages. Areas of integration covered by practice are integration of migrants in the education system; fighting discrimination and promotion of diversity; promoting language skills; valuing linguistic diversity; promoting intercultural openness of institutions</p>
<p>Tailored integration in the education system</p>	<p>Integration of migrant children in Germany (field of education, and language)</p>	<p>Tailored integration process for migrant children and their parents in the education system. This practice implemented by the district of Heilbronn (Germany) has three main elements: Introduction of testing for newly arrived school children, aged</p>

		<p>10-15, to find the most suitable kind of school and make the most of their educational potential</p> <p>Introduction of parent mentors as interpreters for meetings with parents in kindergartens and schools</p> <p>Obtaining funding from the state of Baden-Württemberg and the national level to achieve strategic integration objectives. By testing newly arrived school children, the practice enables individually tailored integration in the education system and prevents discrimination in educational placement based on lack of German-language skills. Parent mentors furthermore strengthen the partnership between newly arrived parents and the kindergarten or school. Since the integration of migrants is a voluntary municipal task, it is important to find sources of funding beyond the municipal budget to expand the scope of sustainable integration efforts.</p>
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4.2 Tackling radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and/or terrorism

Radicalisation hate speech and extremism are complex phenomena and of the major concerns of the Middle East, North Africa (MENA region) and Europe (Bourekba, 2016). There is not one universally accepted definition on these phenomena, as they have different drivers amongst individuals who adopt extreme and radical political, social, or religious ideas and aspirations who reject or undermine the status quo or contemporary ideas and expressions of each country (UNODC, 2018; Böttcher, 2017). These terms are inextricably linked with the threats that are caused due to migrants' false narratives about Europe.

To tackle problems of this nature, coordinated actions are needed at international, European, and national levels. A crucial aspect of the EU's response is the strengthening of its own strategic communication with common narratives and factual representation of conflicts, as well as the establishment of Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN) (European Commission, Migration and Home affairs, 2020) in 2011. RAN engaged several first-line practitioners directly in preventing radicalisation through providing them the opportunity to exchange knowledge and experiences with one another. The threats of radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and terrorist acts are perceived as threats by the host countries, as they are likely to develop among migrant and refugee communities which will eventually be integrated into the host country. These are also viewed as a threat to the safety, integrity, dignity and life of migrants and refugees, as acts of intolerance have been conducted against the latter, such as hate crimes, which in both cases gave rise to campaigns against extremism, radicalisation, hate speech and hate crime.

In this dataset, participants have included 8 entries that address these kinds of issues and are almost evenly distributed among their years of release (2015-2018). The reason why the number of the entries may appear low, is because these entries were explicitly referring to this phenomenon, while under categories 3, 5 and 6 there are some practices that also tackle these kinds of threats combined with other phenomena. 6 out of 10 were implemented on a national level with the rest to have been implemented on a European level, while educational and training sessions, workshops and art driven

initiatives have been most commonly adopted as counter measure activities in most cases. The following table (Table 5) summarizes the key findings of the dataset.

Table 5. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on tackling radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and/or terrorism

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
Creation of counternarratives to online extremism and hate speech and research into the relationship of online and offline actions	Combatting online hate speech and extremism	The Online Civil Courage Initiative is a European initiative challenging hate speech and extremism online founded by Facebook and led by the Institute for Strategic Dialogue alongside grassroot organisations. Working on providing online support to European NGOs and activists working to counter online extremism and hate speech, developing the best methods to create counternarratives to online extremism and hate speech, and assisting research into the relationship between online speech and offline actions to make counter-speech most effective.
Educational and training sessions with youngsters and educators of youngsters of Muslim and/or immigrant background to confront ethnic-nationalist ideologies	Combatting ethnic-nationalist ideologies	Bildmachen.de is a project directed by ufuq.de, a Germany-based NGO, and funded by the Robert Bosch Foundation. Ufuq.de operates at the intersection of education, academia, and public debate. It works primarily with youngsters of Muslim and/or immigrant background: it aims to foster a sense of belonging and to empower them to confront Islamism and ethnic-nationalist ideologies. In addition, ufuq.de organises training sessions and conferences for educators and civil servants on youth cultures, Islam, and Muslims in Germany, and carries out prevention work in local communities and educational institutions. ufuq.de regularly publishes educational material and scientific papers to inform the broader public about issues related to Islam and migration in Germany.
Transferable ‘Counter-Islamophobia Kit’ (CIK), which aims to detail best-practice in countering anti-Muslim hate across the continent.	Addressing Racism and Islamophobia through counternarratives and Muslim participation	Counter-Islamophobia Kit (CIK) project is critically reviewing dominant anti-Muslim narratives and comparing the use and efficacy of prevailing counter-narratives to Islamophobia in eight European Union member states (France, Germany, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Portugal, Greece and the UK). The project was funded by EU. In the initial phase of the Counter- Islamophobia Kit project, it was

		determined that dominant Islamophobic narratives alleged gender inequality. Therefore, regarding counternarratives to Islamophobia across the cases studied in this report, it was found that strategies for countering Islamophobia must allow for the creation of Muslim spaces for the expression of Muslim voices.
Crime prevention policies e.g. “klarkommen!” to prevent juvenile delinquency among migrants and other crime prevention initiatives, such as “Get a curve - give life a chance”	Design of special policies for crime prevention among young migrants/refugees	Klarkommen was launched in Cologne in 2014 by the Ministry of the Interior and included repressive and crime-preventive measures. Unaccompanied children, adolescents and young adults who have entered the country receive help and support (for example on their integration in the labour market), but also stringent consequences regarding their crimes.
Online Counternarratives against radicalisation and extremism to influence young people in Germany, exposed to extremist narratives on social media	Social media representation of radicalisation narratives in islamist and populist phenomena and extremist content	The VIDEOSTAR Project is a project from the Police, Germany utilizing video-based strategies against radicalisation. The project picks up on the topic and develops countermeasures. The project analyses radicalisation narratives in Islamism and populist phenomena in the early radicalisation phase. Extremist content and how it is presented on social media, particularly on YouTube, is of interest. Based on the analysis of this content, the project aims to develop suitable counternarratives or alternative narratives in a format that appeals to young people.
Clip against hate crime appointed to stakeholders	Clip against hate crime	Outraged at the heinous murder of Falikou Coulibaly, president of the Association of Ivorians of Tunisia, which occurred in December 2018, personalities from various backgrounds stood against the scourge of racism in the Maghreb. In a clip directed by Malik Akiana, the collective created by the lawyer Hosni Maati brings to light on the screen the known faces of the footballer Lilian Thuram, the actress Aïssa Maïga, the actor Reda Kateb, the journalist of Arte Nora Hamadi, of the humourist Samia Orosemane, and the imam / lecturer / essayist, Mohamed Bajrafil, the director of the Renovo school, Taoufik Barboucha, and the founder of the association for autists “ Le Relais ”, Daoud Tatou.

<p>Family support professionals advancing the prevention of radicalisation among young Muslims</p>	<p>Radicalisation of Muslim youth</p>	<p>Include professionals of the family support sector in the prevention and tackling of radicalisation, particularly among young people. The focus is particularly on the radicalisation of Muslim youth. This measure can be considered a countermeasure against threats of radicalisation, and also against 'misperceptions' among professionals about radicalisation, identity-formation, and a search for meaning and belonging for young Muslims in Belgium.</p>
<p>A clip against racism, massively spread in Twitter and Facebook raising extremist voices</p>	<p>Clip as a response to extremist voices</p>	<p>A clip in solidarity with sub-Saharan African immigrants in Algeria, by Sadek Bouzinou in cooperation with "Democratoz", a group of Algerian young artists and activists. The clip features collective stories of sub-Saharan African immigrants who had to flee their homelands because of war and havoc. In the previous months of 2017, an online anti-migrant campaign released a hashtag # لا_للافارقة_في_الجزائر "No to Africans in Algeria" which was widely shared on Twitter and Facebook. This song was a response to a virulent campaign born on social networks during the summer of 2017 and launched on World Refugee Day on June 20 calling for expulsions to protect Algerian families and prevent "chaos". The clip aims at countering those racist and extremist voices. It affirms the hospitality of the Algerian people, which shares the same African land, with their brothers who suffer war and turmoil.</p>

4.3 Review of media representations of migrants and other 'fake news'.

'Fake news', based on a broad definition would encompass 'deliberate attempts and distortion of news, the use of filtered versions to promote ideologies, confuse, sow discontent and create polarization' (Martens et. al., 2018). The term even though it tends to be limited used or even avoided as it is closely related with politics, merely describes the intentional distribution of misinformation, thus 'false information' or 'disinformation'. Disinformation' is deliberately propagated false information and, as such, includes what is understood as 'fake news', while 'misinformation' is false information that is unintentionally propagated (Tucker et al., 2018).

According to Google Trends, the frequency of term 'fakes news' has seen significant growth the last 5 years as it is depicted in the figure below. It is worth mentioning that 'fake news' was firstly used as a technique for disinformation via newspaper, however more recently, this issue has also become prominent on the internet.

Figure 6. The frequency of ‘fake news’ according to Google Trends (2004-2020)

The recent insights have shown that not only the term ‘fake news’ but also its impact has become widespread, as people often become misinformed by several websites that are accessible via the internet and distribute untruthful and misleading information. In addition to that, news distributed through online media (portal) and social media networks represented or shaped in the form of short pieces (detached from the full material) are another common way how ‘fake news’ are widespread nowadays which are leading to intentional misunderstandings and creating a toxic environment for information. According to the European Commission Public Consultation on Disinformation and ‘Fake News’ in 2018, more than 97% of the participants reported to have come across ‘fake news’ at least once (European Commission, 2018a). Thus, misinformation has become one of the major challenges for Europe. This is why since 2018, the Commission has been working to implement a set of counteractions to address the increasing spread of online disinformation across EU Member States ensuring the protection of European values and democratic systems. Moreover, various actions, dialogues and working groups have been scheduled based on the Action Plan against Disinformation published by DG CONNECT (European Commission, 2018b).

The following table (Table 6) depicts all the entries relevant to misinformation, including good practice, measures, and tools, which were received during the data collection process conducted within the scope of this deliverable. These refer mainly to journalism providing platforms for the voices of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers themselves to be represented in order to address toxic narratives against them, as well as to the ethical code that journalists have to follow when dealing with such phenomena. Participants documented 14 entries almost evenly distributed among their years of release (2015-2019), with their level of implementation to be mostly on an International (42%) and European (35%) level. Online platforms, educational and training sessions, workshops as well as policy recommendations have been adopted to tackle this phenomenon.

Table 6. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on the review of media representations of migrants and other fake news

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
Workshops and trainings for media professionals, representatives of CSOs and media regulators across Europe	Improve media coverage and journalism capacity on media representations of migration, refugees, religion, and marginalized groups to tackle fake news and counter hate speech, intolerance, racism, and discrimination	#MediaAgainstHate is a Europe-wide campaign led by the European Federation of Journalists (EFJ) and a coalition of civil society organisations. It organised a series of trainings and workshops for media professionals, representatives of CSOs and media regulators across Europe to exchange best practices and promote mutual learning

		and cooperation activities, thus proposing the adoption of appropriate terminology, accurate and complete information, the protection of the identity of refugees and the consultation of experts and organisations.
Workshops and Joint platforms for media	Address migration-related fake news and disinformation on social media	This study led from the Friedrich Ebert Stiftung Buro Budapest discusses a range of case studies on migration-related fake news and disinformation categorised based on the misinformation method used in them, presenting as proposed measure the creation of joint platforms for media operating in a given territory to offer them a chance to self-regulate as well as the organisation of trainings and workshops on this subject.
Workshops, monitoring exercises and e-learning toolkit	Address migration-related fake news and disinformation on social media	Refugee Reporting is a project intended to assess media representation of refugees and migrants in Europe, to bring together the communities of media professionals and refugees to examine how refugees and migrants themselves could be heard and influence coverage of issues affecting their lives, and to examine standards that would promote reporting that respects refugees and migrants. Through a media monitoring exercise which resulted to an e-learning toolkit as well as engagement with refugee-led groups and organisations and media professional, it results to specific recommendations and communication strategies.
Online databases, Labs, workshops, collective actions, and policy recommendations	Address fake news and disinformation on social media (also migration-related)	EU DisinfoLab is a young independent NGO focused on researching and tackling sophisticated disinformation campaigns targeting the EU, its member states, core institutions, and core values. Through its projects and activities, it uses a methodology that relies on Social Network Analysis (SNA), to map social media clusters, monitor and source disinformation, and dynamically visualise an ecosystem to identify key players, clusters, and the spread of disinformation narratives. It also proposes policy recommendations to update the current legal framework in the EU to counter false narratives.
e-Media toolkit (Trainings, webinars, workshops and	Address fake news and disinformation on social media (also migration-related)	This toolkit developed by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) brings together factual reporting examples from different media genres, and practical

online learning to journalists and the public in general)		tools such as checklists. It provides the media with guidance to enhance quality journalism.
Code of Practice on Disinformation	Address fake news and disinformation on social media (also migration-related)	Representatives of online platforms, leading social networks, advertisers, and advertising industry agreed on a self-regulatory Code of Practice to address the spread of online disinformation and fake news.
Handbook for journalism education and training	Address fake news and disinformation (also migrant-related)	This Handbook authored by UNESCO, serves as a model curriculum, and is designed to give journalism educators and trainers, along with students of journalism, a framework, and lessons to help navigate the issues associated with 'fake news'. It draws together the input of leading international journalism educators, researchers and thinkers who are helping to update journalism method and practice to deal with the challenges of misinformation and disinformation.
Online campaign	Address the effect of negative reporting that can occur by presenting a distorted and often negative image of migrants by the media and social media platforms.	EAVI's 'Building Trust' online campaign intends to counter these wide-spread stereotypes that can occur by presenting a distorted and often negative image of migrants by the media and social media platforms by educating the public and highlighting the techniques used that can easily change the context of situations and news reporting. This online campaign aims to combat racism, xenophobia, and hate speech. The targeted groups are between 20-45 years old, either in the Media Literacy community (journalists, researchers, civic society etc.) or people who are part of the migrant and refugee community.
Toolkit for disinformation, Impact analysis, media monitoring and countermeasures	Address fake news and disinformation (also migrant-related)	RESIST Disinformation is a toolkit, the purpose of which is to prevent the spread of disinformation. It is based on a model of recognising disinformation, having situational insights on the context of the disinformation, strategic communication to develop a public response to disinformation, and Early Warning system focused on digital monitoring, an impact analysis based on the likely goal of the disinformation, its likely impact, reach, and finally tracking outcomes.
Recommendations on media	Improve media coverage and journalism capacity on media representations of migration	"MOROCCO: The Invisible People Who Should Take their Place on the Media Stage". This study proposes recommendations on

coverage on migration		media coverage on migration. The main challenge for Moroccan media is to report on progress being made to support this settlement migration and the challenges arising from this new situation, with its ups and downs. In other words, media should guide and support the migratory journey of people living on Moroccan soil in their everyday experience. There should be more focus on the day-to-day realities of their lives as a next-door neighbour, work colleague, teacher, health care system user or job seeker. It is essential for the Moroccan media to discard any media treatment that reflects an image of migration solely in terms of transit or invasion.
Recommendations on media coverage on migration	Improve media coverage and journalism capacity on media representations of migration	Recommendations on media coverage on migration. "ALGERIA: Public Debate Needed to Confront Denial and Media Stereotypes". This study provides recommendations such as: trainings to journalists, chief editors and journalism students on migration; Redefine the media's sources and work more closely with researchers, academics and Algerian research centres, & authorities; Forge more partnerships with NGOs and Algerian associations; Create room for discussion with the local authorities in order to be kept constantly informed; Compile a migration glossary of the terms used.
Stock of existing educational material and best practices, trainings, modules, pan-European awareness-raising campaign "Get your facts straight!" with a launch event in Brussels in March 2020.	Address fake news and disinformation (also migrant-related)	Get Your Facts Straight (GETFACTS) is a project aimed at providing media literacy to students and young people from socially and poor backgrounds, including their parents and grandparents. Workshops will include learning about disinformation and fake news on social media platforms to raise their awareness of different issues. The project will take stock of existing educational materials and best practices, design an outline of media literacy training focused on disinformation and fake news with learning goals and outcomes, train teachers and trainers then run a pan-European awareness-raising campaign.
Report on best practices and tools to address disinformation & malign influence	Address fake news and disinformation (also migrant-related)	Disinformation & Malign Influence Tools & Best Practices: This document compiles tools & best practices to address disinformation & malign influence. It compiles publicly

		available information & resources as well as monitoring tools and training materials
Proposal of several measures such as: Laws against hate speech, combatting disinformation about refugees, Countering the “invasion of hostile aliens” narrative, Messages and messengers, Creating encounters between refugees and host communities, Getting the public involved	Countering toxic narratives about refugees and migrants	Combatting disinformation about refugees: Distorted or “fake” information about refugees and migrants regularly surfaces online. Many companies, media and governments have taken steps to combat fake news. Against powerful voices Hate speech, Incitement to violence, Fear of the “other”, Refugees and migrants as “threat”, Social media, Contexts, questions and public opinion, Audiences matter, Bullying.

4.4 Awareness raising on the migrant journey and the risks associated with irregular migration routes (human trafficking, migrant smuggling, deaths, etc.) along with policies to tackle them

For the majority of migrants, the coveted journey to EU can be extremely unsafe, as smugglers frequently exposing migrants to life-threatening risks. The most common dangers that irregular migrants face on their journey can be categorised in three main categories: physical risks, including their travel using overcrowded boats, or unsafe-for-passenger seats (e.g. inside a truck), financial risks dependant on several factors (e.g. the chosen way to reach Europe, the chosen smuggler to facilitate the trip, the medical assistance that will be needed, etc.) and the other risks which affect specific population groups (e.g. physical abuse that women and children may suffer, etc.).

Over the past years, many deaths have been recorded within the borders of the Mediterranean Sea, in parallel with the increasing rate of human trafficking and smuggling incidents (Missing Migrants, 2020). This is one of the reasons why the European Union for at least one decade has already implemented several changes on legislation and policies or funded initiatives and action plans, such as the Action Plan against Migrant Smuggling (European Commission, 2015b), which was designed to transform smuggling from a 'high profit, low risk' business into a 'high risk, low profit' business, while ensuring the full respect and protection of migrants' basic human rights.

The following table (Table 7) includes the collected good practices that aim to raise migrants' awareness regarding the risks that they may face during their journey to Europe. It also presents the policies and legislation changes needed to address the threats of human trafficking, smuggling and deaths of migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees, as good practices. These include trainings to LEAs;

cooperation among authorities of neighbouring countries to fight border crime; border controls and interagency cooperation; police investigations and prosecution of criminal offences of smuggling and human trafficking and implementation of the EU Directive against trafficking.

The majority of the entries (37 out of 149) have been documented under this category, with most of them being released after 2017 (81%). Governmental and policy making organisations have mostly proposing such practices (51.3%) with civil society and NGOs follow (35.1%). 24 out of 37 entries include practices, measures and tools implemented on a national level, both for countries of origin and host/destination countries, while campaigns, art-based initiatives and targeted websites have been mostly utilised to tackle this phenomenon.

Table 7. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on awareness raising on the migrant journey and the risks associated with irregular migration routes (human trafficking, migrant smuggling, deaths, etc.) along with policies to tackle them

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
Campaigns	Awareness raising of risks associated to the journeys to Europe	Youth and Development (Jovenes y Desarrollo) ONGD Salesiana organised a campaign called Stop Naufragios (Stop shipwrecks), aiming to raise awareness amongst Ethiopian youth of the real risks associated with the journey to Europe, via educational sessions.
Action Plan on the use of Social Media against migrant smuggling	Awareness raising material around migrant smuggling	This Action plan issued by the European Migration Network summarizes the results of the Ad-Hoc Query and the discussions held at the workshop, with the main aim to provide an overview of the use of social media in migrant smuggling. More specifically, it explores how social media is used for the purpose of migrant smuggling, and how it is used by Member States and other key stakeholders in their efforts to prevent and investigate smuggling activities.
Awareness raising Campaigns to potential irregular migrants	Awareness raising of risks associated to the journeys to Europe and the reality of migration to Europe	Deterrence campaigns organised by European Values Protecting Freedom and Wilfried Martens Centre for European Studies directed at migrants to combat a false idea of a better life in Europe, raise awareness of the reality of migration, and protect them from false narratives offered by smuggling networks.
Strategic communications campaigns (diaspora-based online communication, TV, radio, social media)	Raise awareness and influence existing perceptions of West African migrants on migration to Europe	This study by the Directorate General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG Home) focuses on communication channels used by migrants and asylum seekers in West Africa to obtain information in countries of origin and transit, with particular focus

<p>campaigns, community interventions)</p>		<p>on online and social media. The study findings support the development of a strategic communications campaign aimed at influencing migratory choices in countries of origin and transit. The implementation strategies varied from diaspora-based online communication, TV, radio, social media campaigns, community interventions and targeting key family/community members.</p>
<p>Training days in humanitarian/migration centers, social media posts and mobile phones messages</p>	<p>Awareness raising of risks associated to the journeys to Europe (irregular migration)</p>	<p>The report by the Directorate General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG Home) focuses at irregular migration to Italy from Nigeria, Bangladesh, Gambia, Mali, Senegal and others providing a comprehensive analysis of the information and communication channels that migrants use upon their arrival in Italy, and which may help determine their secondary movements. It also presents recommendations involving the development of more effective mechanisms for migration information dissemination and for awareness-raising campaigns and trainings for migrants and staff at reception centres within the context of the EU's Action Plan against Migrant Smuggling. In addition to that it proposes the use of mobiles, social media, and technology in general to assess the risks of irregular migration.</p>
<p>Mobile cinema screenings</p>	<p>Raise awareness about the reality surrounding migration, especially the serious risks that migrants face during their travels in small and distant African villages.</p>	<p>CinemArena us a project by the Italian Foreign Ministry, in collaboration with the International Organization for Migration and the Italian Interior Ministry, which aims to educate potential migrants in small villages in Africa about the dangers of undertaking the migrant journey. The project, CinemArena, travels to small villages in Africa and uses film as the medium for raising awareness about the reality surrounding migration.</p>
<p>News articles, videos, mini-documentaries, and interviews shared a web platform and on different social networks in five languages: French,</p>	<p>Raise awareness and counter misinformation on the risks of migration</p>	<p>InfoMigrants is a news and information site for migrants to counter misinformation at every point of their journey: in their country of origin, along the route, or in the places where they hope to start a new life. InfoMigrants is available in five languages: French, Arabic, English, Dari, and Pashto. Its aim is</p>

Arabic, English, Dari, and Pashto.		to supply migrants with reliable, verified, objective and balanced news and information about the countries they have left, the countries they travel through, and the countries to which they are headed.
Theatrical plays as a communication mean of awareness raising	Raise awareness the risks and myths surrounding irregular migration from Tunisia to Europe	An initiative from the IOM based on using theatre to tackle the risks and myths surrounding irregular migration by following the lives, aspirations, and disappointments of migrants in the play. The theater plays took place in 4 different locations based on the myths and risks of irregular migration from Tunisia to Europe, with debate and discussion with the participants after the plays.
Baseline Study report on trafficking in Tunisia	Raise awareness on trafficking (indirect effect to migrants) - Tunisia	This baseline Study from International Organisation for Migration and Republic of Tunisia aims to be a key step in supporting all the actors involved in the fight against trafficking. It helped to develop 18 recommendations to strengthen action in Tunisia to prevent trafficking.
Awareness raising campaign against human trafficking (incl. Videos, photo exhibition) and for the dangers of irregular migration	Human trafficking and irregular migration	Awareness raising campaign “Together against Human Trafficking” that consists of a collection of animation videos explaining the forms of the crime in Egypt, encouraging citizens to report it, and defining the relevant penalties stated in Law no 64/2010. Photo exhibition that displays the forms of human trafficking in Egypt was shown on various occasions such as the commemoration of the World day against human trafficking, United Nations Week at Future University, Development Conference for Peace and Migration Film Festival.
Border controls – interdepartmental and interagency cooperation	Policies for dealing with smuggling against migrants and criminality	Border controls at the German Schengen external borders / searches at the internal borders and in trains as well as in the area of railway facilities / cooperation between the Federal Police, the police forces of the Länder and the Federal Customs Administration in the border areas in various forms, e.g. joint investigation teams and joint centres of police and customs cooperation / effective investigations and analysis of the situation by the Federal Police, the

		Federal Criminal Police Office and the competent authorities at state level / holistic, interdepartmental and interagency analysis of smuggling of migrants and related criminal phenomena in the Joint Analysis and Strategy Centre for Illegal Migration (GASIM) with the participation of the Federal Police, the Federal Criminal Police Office, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, the Federal Intelligence Service, the Federal Customs Administration (Financial Control of Undeclared Work), the Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution and the Federal Foreign Office
Website that provides accurate information on what refugees can expect from Germany (in terms of risks, legal and practical dimensions) aiming at informing and not deterring	Journey to Europe risks, legal, practical dimensions	This website of the German Federal Foreign Office is the central informational resource of the ongoing information campaign that Germany conducts since 2015 to ensure that potential and current migrants, as well as their communities, do not have to rely on false information and rumours spread by people smugglers. The goal of the website is not to deter, but to inform. The decision to embark on the dangerous journey to Europe is such an important one that it should be based on facts, not rumours. Unfortunately, many irregular migrants make the decision to set out for Europe based on inaccurate information and rumours spread by people smugglers who are interested in profit, not the benefit and safety of the migrants. This website aims to counter rumours with an accurate description of the reality of irregular migration towards Europe. It covers the real cost and risks of the journey, the legal and practical dimensions of applying for asylum in Germany as well as the facts on who might be granted protection status and permission to work, and who is unlikely to be granted the right to stay in Germany and thus, will have to return home.
Apps, art (theatre), and capacity building workshops from country of departure to promote socio-	Incentives for citizens in their country of departure	AwArtMali aims to contribute to the change of perceptions and behaviour of Malian people looking to irregular migration towards the EU as the only solution to their socio-economic

<p>economic opportunities for citizens to stay in their country of departure</p>		<p>problems. The action is intended to reach and involve Malian people in order to make them aware and inform them on the risks of irregular migration, on legal alternatives and on economic opportunities available in their country with a multi-stakeholder approach consisting in awareness campaign and information activities. Current activities include a travelling theatre group, capacity building workshops, the creation of an app to keep target groups up to date on socio-economic opportunities in Mali, a video documentary collecting testimonies of the Malian diasporas in Spain and Italy.</p>
<p>Policy appointed to stakeholders on conducting awareness campaigns on the dangers of irregular migration</p>	<p>Awareness campaigns and programmes to inform the youth about the true realities of the situation in Europe</p>	<p>Policy that makes proposals to all kinds of stakeholders (border security officers, LEA, researchers etc.). Among them, the need is stressed to undertake awareness campaigns for the prevention of irregular migration; provide information for the benefit of would-be migrants; create awareness of the dangers inherent in irregular migration. One can argue that this would imply countering false narratives about migration that may be spread among Nigerians. Perceptions expressly mentioned at two points: Institute intensive advocacy and awareness programmes to inform the youth about the true realities of the situation in Europe and to demystify the perception of youths about the opportunities and job prospects in Europe and that the roads of EU countries are “paved with gold”; Xenophobia: Attitudes, prejudices and behaviour that reject, exclude and often vilify persons, based on the perception that they are outsiders or foreigners to the community, society or national identity.</p>
<p>Direct testimonies of returned migrants as information campaign against disinformation on irregular migration; dangers and difficulties sharing among compatriots</p>	<p>Dangers and difficulties of the migration journey</p>	<p>Youth against irregular migrations (YAIM) is an association officially formed by a group of young Gambians repatriated from Libya in 2017, the scope of the information activities of the group is to increase awareness on irregular migration and help in the reducing the incidence of irregular migration. The idea behind the information campaign of YAIM is the</p>

		<p>sharing of the experiences lived in first person by the creators, young people who have experienced the danger of the journey, have lived in Libya and have managed to return to Gambia. The purpose of the campaign is to spread news about dangers and difficulties, through the sharing of the experience among compatriots, in order spread a realistic imaginary and narrative about migration. The group, to spread its own campaign, uses various ICTs sources such as radio and social networks; in particular, the information is shared on a Facebook page, but the group is also active through more direct awareness activities. Specifically, an itinerant campaign was implemented in Gambia.</p>
<p>Programmes in countries of arrival, transit, and departure for migrants to be aware of the risks around migration and what to expect and providing alternatives to migration</p>	<p>Risks and alternatives to irregular migration</p>	<p>"Free to leave, free to stay"- "Liberi di partire, liberi di restare" is a campaign that supports 14 projects in Italy, country of arrival; 6 projects in transit migration countries, entrusted to the Caritas of Niger, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco, but also Albania and - managed by Italian Caritas - in Turkey. Finally, 12 other projects are directly financed in the countries of departure: Mali, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Gambia, Guinea and managed by development cooperation entities such as Vis, Vides, Avsi or local Caritas. The latter projects, to improve awareness, are supported in schools, squares, markets and are focused on the risks of relying on traffickers, they use with posters, informative material, commercials. The aim is to return correct information on migration issue. At the same time, thanks to the Salesian NGOs, the projects include professional training to create electricians, mechanics, farmers and insert them into the world of work, offering an alternative to emigration. The projects in the countries in transit also provide accompaniment to return home for those who decide freely. In Italy, dioceses and orders manage numerous reception projects. Priority domains will include: education and training (including vocational training), on-site information (on what it means to migrate), targeted</p>

		social and healthcare projects for the weakest segments of the migrant population (minors and victims of human trafficking in particular), socio-economic projects to promote job opportunities, and support people who voluntarily want to go back to their countries.
Campaign on human trafficking and travel risks of migration journey and provision of alternatives to migration (economic and labour in country of departure) on the field through meetings in schools, artistic events, information meetings on local opportunities	Human trafficking, irregular migration, alternatives to migration	VIS organization has organized "STOP TRATTA" campaign. The aim of the campaign is to reduce human trafficking, creating awareness among potential migrants and sharing and creating opportunities on the territory. The constant presence on the territory is one of the strengths of the "Stop Tratta" campaign. This is the case of "Vivre et Reussir chez moi", born from the need to prevent irregular migration, to combat the trafficking of human beings and to help govern migration flows by offering economic and labour alternatives to migration. The ultimate goal is to combat trafficking in human beings also through information and awareness-raising actions about travel risks and the consequences of traffic. Volunteers began awareness-raising activities in the Tambacounda region through working groups with rural youth. VIS operators involve young people, potential migrants or returning migrants, presenting the opportunities and potential of the territory in terms of vocational training and employment to make young people understand that it is possible to develop economic activities in their territory of origin.
Change of national legislations to be in compliance with the EU Directive against human trafficking. Implementation of the Directive	Human trafficking legislation	Germany has changed its legislation in accordance with the EU Directive against human trafficking, as all EU MS shall do. Still, there are implementation challenges.
Change of legislation and policies on human trafficking and EU cities as 'safe harbours'	Asylum, integration, human trafficking, 'safe harbours'	Changes of national legislation on asylum, integration, human trafficking and policies such as the identification of certain EU cities as 'safe harbours'

<p>Policies to combat human trafficking against migrants; conduct of studies, participations to workshops, trainings to LEAs; investigation by Police; cooperation among counsellors and the Police; Cooperation along EU MS</p>	<p>Human trafficking</p>	<p>Police support with the states' national measures: Provision of comprehensive information and scientific studies on the subject; Special evaluations and extensive investigation procedures; Development, implementation and dissemination of concepts for victim protection and cooperation between specialist counselling centres and the Police; Participation in the Federal-State Working Group on Trafficking in Human Beings annual workshops and extensive training and further training and Bilateral cooperation with EU Member States and the countries of origin of trafficked persons</p>
<p>Cooperation among authorities of neighbouring countries to fight border crime; trainings to stakeholders; investigation and prosecution of criminal offences of smuggling and human trafficking</p>	<p>Migrant Smuggling and human trafficking</p>	<p>Project to raise the effectiveness of and the cooperation among regional and national institutions in fighting serious and organised crime, mainly migrant smuggling, enhancing cooperation and better communication between countries. Preventing migrant smuggling would presumably affect the spread of false narratives on Europe indirectly. A prosecutor and a police officer to help each relevant Western Balkan institution to prosecute and investigate crimes, along with short-term practical trainings.</p>
<p>Information campaign through Website and Facebook page managed by the Belgium Service</p>	<p>Journey to Europe risks, legal, practical dimensions</p>	<p>Information campaign managed by the Immigration Service under supervision of the State Secretary for Asylum and Migration that aims to inform potential and current migrants about the Belgian legislation and procedures regarding migration. "Informing potential migrants about the real facts about migration is essential in the battle against the false information and rumours spread by people smugglers. The overall goal of the campaign is to provide correct information and facts, so migrants can make a well-informed choice regarding leaving their country of origin."</p>
<p>TV advertisement with a famous footballer telling about the risks of illegal migration and social media campaign.</p>	<p>Dangers and difficulties of the migration journey</p>	<p>National awareness raising campaign by the IOM and the National Coordinating Committee on Combatting and Preventing Illegal Migration and Trafficking in Persons (NCCPIM&TIP) on the risks of irregular migration of Egyptian</p>

		youth and children, using a combination of digital and traditional media to maximize reach and impact.
Workshops, awareness raising days, forums, and trainings	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Algeria	One Awareness day and one workshop, one national forum and the Eighth National Forum on illegal Migration among Algerian Youth, all organised in Algeria for irregular migration (4 entries). Since 2018, these initiatives become more frequent, in order to guide and aware especially young people about the danger of the illegal migration, in the other hand, they highlight the fact that people can't really find what they are expecting in an easy way, so they stay in their country, and try to make their situations better by taking advantage of the facilities granted by the state for investment such as loans ANSEJ and ANJEM.
Campaigns and field visits to the governorates	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Egypt	Launching of a direct dialogue with the Egyptian Youth, organized under the campaign "Egypt is your future" to raise the awareness of youth on the risks of illegal migration as well as the alternatives they can rely on to improve their social and economic conditions
Workshops	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Egypt	Organization of capacity building workshops for diplomats, Media professionals, Civil Society and prosecutors and participation in almost 20 national and international events dealing with illegal migration, for supporting groups that play a significant role in endorsing NCCPIM mandate.
Roadshows, street plays and seminars, distribution of materials at public places, among others, involving dept. Govt officials, Police, and potential migrants	Awareness raising on irregular migration - India	Campaign to spread awareness on the consequences of Unsafe (Irregular) Migration from the state of Punjab to Europe, engaging population and relevant stakeholders in dialogues and community participation to exchange information and sensitize potential migrants. This Awareness campaign covers 46 villages in 26 Blocks of 13 Districts in the State of Punjab based on hotspots identified. It will engage with communities and various stakeholders in Punjab.

Newspaper entry	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Morocco	Combating illegal immigration through the media an analytical study case of the daily El Chourouk newspaper during 2017
Awareness raising campaigns	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Gambia	Awareness raising campaign held in The Gambia to inform potential migrants about the dangers and risks of migrating irregularly to Europe, aimed at discouraging young people from undertaking the journey.
A song by two famous Egyptian artists and drama series in several radio programmes and radio series on different radio channels tackling the issue of illegal migration	Awareness raising on irregular migration - Egypt	Awareness raising campaign in social media and radio programmes tackling the issue of illegal migration.
Arts-based methods as social research tools (photo galleries, exhibitions, videos, festivals, toolkits)	Awareness raising on forced displacement - Morocco	Arts for Advocacy' is an inter-disciplinary research project funded by the Global Challenges Research Fund at the universities of Edinburgh and Keele. It seeks to develop innovative, interdisciplinary, and participatory arts-based methods to facilitate critical engagement and advocacy relating to forced displacement in Morocco. The project objectives are: to generate fresh empirical and theoretical insights on the politics of displacement, transition, and resettlement in Morocco and evaluate the broader social relevance of creative arts-based methods; to enhance the research and advocacy capacity of local and national NGOs working in support of displaced communities in Morocco through sustainable engagement and advocacy programmes; to enhance the advocacy capacity of grassroots migrants' associations; to build relationships, develop partnerships, and exchange best practice transnationally between Morocco and the UK and across academia and the third sector working on forced displacement. This project was awarded the Best Practice Knowledge Exchange in the Glasgow Refugee Festival (June 2017). During this project, an exhibition took place in Rabat in March and October 2017, displaying the production of some twenty participants of different

		nationalities, retracing the stories of journeys, obstacles, relationships, love, broken dreams, and new hopes. (2 entries)
Art exhibitions	Raise awareness on dangers of migration - Algeria	A series of art exhibitions organised every two years by Sadiq Rahim, a contemporary Algerian artist, since 2011, to raise awareness in Arab and African youth not to risk their lives and migrate to Europe
Seminar	Raise awareness on dangers of irregular migration - Egypt	The Media Coverage of Illegal Migration: “Challenges and Alternatives” The National Coordinating Committee on Combating and Preventing Illegal Migration NCCPIM, in cooperation with the Radio and T.V. Union and the International Organization of Migration IOM, held a seminar on May 24th, 2015 targeting Media Professionals to discuss best approaches for Media to cover illegal migration. There took place an analysis of the way the local media is addressing the issue of illegal migration in order to identify the gaps and best approaches to be adopted in this field.

4.5 Addressing negative public perceptions, racism, and xenophobia towards migrants in the host country

The terms “racism” and “xenophobia” are defined as the belief that race, colour, descent, religion, or belief, national or ethnic origin act as a factor determining aversion to individuals or groups (European Commission, 2001).

Racism, intolerance and xenophobia foster hate and violence against specific groups including migrants and result to extreme risks for both migrants and the host country. In many countries, migrants constitute a specific group of people which natives classify as ‘the others’ who are treated as a significant threat to a unified national ethnic identity. This behaviour leads to their discrimination due to their own values, traditions and the cultural, racial differences that they have from the dominant group of mainstream society; the policymakers claim that these differences come as a direct conflict with the population of host country.

During the past 25 years European Commission Against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI) have provided all the governments of EU MS with detailed guidelines and policies, monitoring them in parallel so as to report any shortfalls, issues derived from ECRI’s findings in each EU country. In addition, to attempting to successfully counter racism and xenophobia, several pieces of EU legislation (European Commission, 2019) have been released such as:

- the Victims' Rights Directive (Council directive 2012/29/EU, 2012) which establishes minimum standards on the rights, support, and protection of all victims of crime, paying particular attention to victims who have suffered a crime committed with a bias or discriminatory motive
- the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (Council directive 2010/12/EU, 2010), banning incitement to hatred in audiovisual media services and the promotion of discrimination in audiovisual commercial communications
- legislation in the area of non-discrimination, in particular the Race Equality Directive (Council Directive 2000/43/EC, 2000a) prohibiting discrimination on grounds of racial or ethnic origin in several walks of life, and the Employment Equality Directive (Council Directive 2000/78/EC, 2000b) prohibiting discrimination on several grounds in the field of employment
- legislation prohibiting discrimination during border controls

However, there are also several coordinated actions dedicated to specific target groups (e.g. religious groups including Muslims), to tackle negative public perceptions towards them either on a national or on European and international level. Plenty of these actions and good practices are identified within the scope of this deliverable and can be found in the following table (Table 8). Twenty-four (24) entries have addressed the aforementioned phenomena, half of these have been released since 2018 and 62% of these describe practices implemented on a national level. Trainings, online platforms for story and data sharing, campaigns, and art-driven programs, as well as reports with recommendations are but some of the proposed measures mostly presented by Civil society and NGOs (58.3%).

Table 8. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on addressing negative public perceptions, racism, and xenophobia towards migrants in the host country

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
Factsheet with FAG	Address myths about migration	This factsheet collects the most common fiction and most common myths about migration to Europe and addresses them with the proper information.
Recreational and cultural activities	Address feelings of xenophobia of people in Milan towards refugees and asylum seekers	Zona 8 Solidale is a network created in September 2016 in Milan. It includes associations, parties, trade unions, activists, and individual, the purpose of which to experiment forms of active citizenship aimed at welcoming refugees and it is inspired by 2 principles: anti-racism and participation. Zona 8Solidale carries out numerous recreational and cultural activities on various fronts, merged into the network "No one is illegal". Its main aim is that in order to stop racism episodes, it is necessary to show the citizens that the arrival of new citizens is an opportunity to start positive processes of sociality and solidarity;
Online platform of migrant stories	Address myths and perceptions that UK citizens have towards migrants	Movement Against Xenophobia and Joint Council for the Welfare of Immigrants (supported by the IOM) have created this online platform which seeks to challenge the

		negative narratives on migration in the UK, celebrate them and provide them with a platform to share their personal stories.
Trainings to Moroccan authorities	Prevention of racism and xenophobia against migrants in Morocco	The project "Vivre ensemble sans discrimination" [Living together without discrimination] aims at tackling racism and xenophobia in Morocco. Based on the protection of fundamental rights and paying special attention to the gender perspective, the project seeks to strengthen public instruments and policies aimed at preventing & tackling racism and xenophobia towards the migrant population. In order to involve Moroccan institutions in the development of the project, the different work commissions were e created. These monitored and guided the activities, guaranteeing the involvement of the Moroccan administration and its mainstreaming in public policies.
Campaign appointed to stakeholders (LEAs, Border control agencies, NGOs, General public, Public agencies)	Campaign against xenophobia	A targeted campaign such as the Somos Panas (We are Friends) campaign in Colombia aimed to reduce manifestations of xenophobia towards Venezuelans living in the country. The campaign promotes messages of solidarity from Colombians to Venezuelan children, women, and men, as well as messages of gratitude received from Venezuelans. Since its launch in December 2017, the campaign has reached more than six million people and over 235,000 opinion leaders and members of the government.
Study for public attitudes towards migration and recommendations	Provide a better understanding of public attitudes towards migration	This study published by the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) aims to provide a better understanding of public attitudes towards migration in 17 selected countries on both sides of the Mediterranean and to explain what accounts for these attitudes, with an emphasis on the role of the media. The report summarises previous findings, provides new analyses and makes recommendations on how to communicate on migration in a non-polarising manner.
Network of refugee communities, NGO organisations and individuals	Reduce discrimination and prejudices towards refugees	RISE – Refugees Ideas and Solutions for Europe – is a network created in 2016, led by refugee communities, organisations, and individuals in different European countries. RISE has today 22 network members from 14 different countries. RISE represents the authentic voices of refugees, where refugees

		<p>campaign for themselves. Through various actions, its overall aim revolves around contributing to make refugees full members of their society – in which they are not only actively involved, but also recognised as knowledgeable, skilled, and experienced people. The RISE network aims at reducing discrimination and prejudices towards refugees by deconstructing old narratives on refugees and creating new perceptions in societies. The ultimate goal of RISE is that refugees will have a decent life in Europe as full member of the society, self-determined and recognized as human beings with skills, experiences, ideas, and thoughts.</p>
<p>Trans-Maghreb campaign against racism: Conferences, press announcements, workshops, artistic events for the elimination of all the forms of racial discrimination appointed to political decision-makers, the media and public opinion.</p>	<p>Elimination of racial discrimination Campaign</p>	<p>Trans-Maghreb campaign against racism Conferences, press announcements, workshops, artistic events, etc, across Maghreb countries. This first Trans-Maghreb Campaign against Racism intended to federate all the dynamics which advocate for the elimination of all the forms of racial discrimination in the Maghreb space between nationals but also and especially with regard to the migrants and refugees of sub-Saharan Africa. This campaign also aimed at raising awareness among political decision-makers, the media and public opinion as to the seriousness of certain discriminatory acts and remarks which have become commonplace in daily practice.</p>
<p>MOROCCO: Concert for Tolerance</p>	<p>Tolerance</p>	<p>The Concert for Tolerance [Concert pour la Tolérance] is an event organized by national artists and international organisations in Agadir. An event representing Peace, Love, Tolerance and Fraternity in the world</p>
<p>Video Bladi bladek (My country is yours) by Leila Alaoui on social media</p>	<p>Tackle racism in Algeria</p>	<p>A clip denouncing the daily racism that sub-Saharan migrants suffer in Morocco. Even though the three Moroccan national television channels (Médi1 TV, 2M and Al Aoula) refused to broadcast it, it was massively distributed through social media</p>
<p>Videos in social media & citizens wearing pins in their clothes</p>	<p>Tackle racism in Algeria</p>	<p>A video shared online urges Algerians to sign a petition condemning the Algerian Football Federation which announced that dual nationals considered for selection would have to display an "unconditional commitment to Algeria" and be technically superior to players living in Algeria. The</p>

		narrator of the video says that racism is a crime, not an opinion in order to create awareness and calling the viewers to sign the petition.
Recommendations for more evidence-based policy	Tackle perception and myths around migrants in Belgium	The report states that largely negative view on migration and a lack of insight into the causes and consequences of migration have led to a number of widespread "migration myths" that have gained a status of truth and shape public perception and inform policy. The report tackles three persistent 'myths' i) development cooperation will stop migration, ii) closing the borders will stop migration, iii) restricting the rights of migrants is necessary to maintain society; and calls for more evidence-based policy. Thus, it could be considered a 'countermeasure' against widespread myths or 'false narratives' about migration.
Easily accessible empirically based arguments to challenge existing prejudices and 'misperceptions' about migration in Belgium.	Tackle existing prejudices and 'misperceptions' about migration in Belgium	Publicly available book that aims to tackle prejudices about migration that exist among the general population in Belgium.
Video clips / films; Course / Training Toolbox of online resources for adult educators; collection of drama and theatre games and exercises and how they can be used to promote equality, inclusion, and anti-racism work	Address issues of rising inequality and racism and the lack of inclusion for marginalized groups	The Drama for Change products provide adult educators, teachers, and artists with the skills necessary to work with adults through a creative medium, using drama and theatre to promote anti-racism, gender equality and diversity. They teach how to use drama and theatre techniques in their work with adult learners, providing a list of drama and theatre games and exercises including a Step-by-Step Guide and functions. The project aims include: to develop a training curriculum to provide adult educators with the skills necessary to work with young people and adults; to use creative processes to address issues of rising inequality and racism and the lack of inclusion for marginalized groups; to promote social inclusion, gender equality and anti-racism work
Public events, workshops, talks, media engagement	Address public perception for migrants in UK (migrant-led project)	The Outsider Project supported migrants affected by the negative discourse around immigration, and promoted a positive narrative demonstrating the benefits of living

		<p>in an open society where migration is commonplace. Throughout the project the teams worked to build relationships with stakeholders, local organisations, policy makers, and non-migrant communities to promote a positive narrative around migration, as well as focusing on engaging local media to increase positive coverage of migrant-led action. Overall, the Outsider project aimed at supporting migrants by engaging local media as well as policy makers, decision makers and local stakeholders, and through holding public events. Specifically:</p> <p>A. Media engagement:</p> <p>Local, positive media coverage of the project and its activities was identified as a keyway of changing the narrative around migration within the local areas. To achieve this, Migrant Leaders were trained as spokespersons for their local communities and were put forward for interview opportunities about migration issues, press releases were sent to local media outlets ahead of all public events and reports, and invitations to attend community events were extended to local journalists</p> <p>B. Policy and Decision Maker Engagement:</p> <p>The Outsider Project also aimed to change the narrative around migration by engaging local policy and decision makers and encouraging them to advocate for the rights of migrants and both local and national level. In each area, local councillors and MPs were engaged where appropriate with the project to achieve this aim.</p>
<p>Report</p>	<p>Address perceptions of Cypriots about Refugees and Migrants</p>	<p>This study was undertaken by the University of Cyprus Centre for Field Studies (UCFS), for the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) in Cyprus between September and December 2018, in order to study perceptions of and attitudes towards refugees and migrants across the Cypriot society. This was done through an analysis of public opinion in the two communities of Cyprus around relevant issues. A similar study was commissioned by UNHCR in 2015; one purpose of the present study was therefore to observe and analyse any changes in attitudes during the three-</p>

		year period, and highlight any trends observed. UNHCR will use the findings to develop specific and informed strategies in their ongoing protection and advocacy work on the island.
Report	Address perceptions of Greeks about Refugees and Migrants	This report provides insight into the attitudes of Greek people towards their country and its place in the world, their sense of national identity, and their views on immigration and refugees. It builds on other recent research into these issues and provides a deeper understanding of the connections between Greeks' perspectives on these and other matters.
Evidence based research for policies reforms	Address perceptions of EU citizens about Refugees and Migrants	Review report of existing perceptions for migrants and proposal of future recommendations and policies reform in the EU to counter the negative perception of migrants
Awareness campaign, training people in social media, activities to promote respect	Address perceptions about Refugees and Migrants (racism, xenophobia etc.)	Al Wassit (For the integration against xenophobia), is a project provides for training activities for the integration of migrants, against all forms of xenophobia. It aims at promoting the integration of immigrants, training people in social media to fight the stereotypes and organize debates, interactive meetings and seminars on diversity and respect to other cultures.
Workshops, sport and artistic activities	Address perceptions about Refugees and Migrants (racism, xenophobia etc.) in Morocco	This initiative is an awareness-raising session for the Moroccan youth on the theme of human rights, asylum, and migration throughout 6 Moroccan cities. They comprised of workshops which intended to promote the values of living together, and to raise awareness on the importance of improving the social and cultural conditions of refugees within the Moroccan community. The overall objective of the project is to promote the values of living together in Morocco, to meet the challenges of protection and to promote cohesion between young refugees and young Moroccans through awareness raising, artistic and sport activities.
Film Screening & Arts performance	Address perceptions about Refugees and Migrants (racism, xenophobia etc.) in Morocco	Between the years 2010 and 2018 the Antiracist Group for Support and Defence of Migrants (Groupe antiraciste d'accompagnement et de défense des migrants-GADEM) and the multidisciplinary

		<p>art company Dabateatr have organized the Migrant'scène - Rabat festival in partnership with the support of Cimade. It echoes the Migrant'scène festival initiated and organized by Cimade in France since 2006. The festival aims to promote the meeting between the different populations present in Morocco and is an opportunity for exchange, sharing and reflection around issues related to migration, cultural confluences, and the specific situation of Morocco as a migration hub. Since its first edition, the festival has emphasized the diversity that is present among the public, on stage (participation of amateur and professional artists and people of different nationalities in creations and residences) and in the organisation of the festival. In 2018 the festival was banned by the authorities</p>
Interactive tool	<p>Address perceptions and false narratives about rejected asylum seekers and issues of return and deportation in Belgium</p>	<p>The Flemish public broadcaster developed an interactive online tool that allows the general public to take the position of migrants who are no longer allowed to stay in Belgium and have to make decisions about staying in Belgium or leaving. The tool is developed in a context of relatively low return rates of rejected asylum seekers and illustrates the complexity of migrants in this situation.</p>
Interactive trainings and other tools	<p>Address perceptions and false narratives about migration in Belgium</p>	<p>Interactive training (tailored made to each organisation) and information sessions on a) how to deal with diversity in organisations, b) information on migration and migration trajectories and c) intercultural communication and reference frameworks. These training gives to Belgium organisations an insight into the migration history to and from Antwerp, the impact migration flows had and still have on newcomers, but also on Antwerp society, so as to deal with the positive and negative aspects of diversity.</p>
Street Theatre in the cities of Casablanca, Rabat, Agadir, Tanger, Fès & Nador	<p>Address perceptions and false narratives about migration in Morocco</p>	<p>Mix city aims at fighting in the public space against prejudices that touch sub-Saharan citizens in Morocco through artistic creation. This project takes the form of a play, created in the style of the "halqa"(traditional Moroccan street theatre) in order to interact with the audience and encourage people to reflect on these situations. The actors are not</p>

		only Moroccan, but also Sub-Saharan migrants who offer their testimony, fruit of their experience of crossing to Morocco, on the dreams of these migrants, of Europe become inaccessible Stories of precariousness that end in Morocco, often in conditions far from ideal.
Cafe and cooking sessions at Lloyd Park.	Address perceptions and false narratives about migration in UK	Stories and Supper is a refugee and migrant supper club project based in Walthamstow, East London which seeks to challenge the myths surrounding the migration 'crisis' and provide a welcome space for refugees living in London. Set up in 2017 they hold supper club events around East London, giving refugees chefs the chance to cook for paying guests

4.6 Protection of human rights of migrants and against other threats related to them in the host country (policies)

Several human rights of migrants and refugees, guaranteed under regional and international law instruments, are unlawfully interfered with throughout their journey to Europe. Indicatively, according to European Court of Human Rights, 2019 (European Court of Human Rights, 2019), it is worth mentioning:

- the freedom from torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment;
- their right not to be held in slavery or servitude;
- their right not to perform forced or compulsory labour (e.g. human trafficking);
- their right to private and family life, home, or correspondence;
- their right to liberty of movement and freedom to choose their residence;
- the freedom to leave any country, including their own;
- the prohibition of collective expulsion; the right to asylum; the principle of non-refoulement
- the right to liberty and security of a person; the right to life;
- the right to access to an effective remedy;
- the abolition of death penalty;
- the prohibition of discrimination on any ground such as sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth, or other status;
- the right to found a family; economic and social rights of migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees, such as the right to work, the right to an adequate standard of living, including food, clothing, and housing, the right to physical and mental health, the right to social security, the right to a healthy environment, and the right to education.

As demonstrated above, the spectrum of violations of migrants', asylum-seekers' and refugees' rights is very broad, and refers to the starting point of their journey to Europe until their potential refoulement, this subsection focuses on the rights not covered in the previous categories as special issues and specifically on the best practices associated with their experiences upon their arrivals. In

many findings, recommendations and good practices include: the fair distribution of responsibilities among EU MS for practical, humanitarian (equipment and personnel) and financial assistance to the countries of first entry, but also for hosting migrants, asylum seekers and refugees, accompanied by the recommendation of the revision of Dublin Regulation on the issue of the responsibility of the country of first entry on examining an application for international protection and on establishing a mechanism for sharing of responsibilities among EU MS (Radjenovic, 2019). Recommendations are also appointed to state authorities in order to comply with their international obligations, including the Law Enforcement Agencies' duties to rescue migrants' at sea through SAR, to ensure their safe disembarkation and safe relocation, the prohibition of pushbacks or returns to unsafe countries, the avoidance of excessive use of force, the assistance in filing applications for international protection before the competent authorities' and the cooperation with other national and regional authorities. Moreover, it is stressed that EU MS must ensure that there are adequate, appropriately located, and safe Border Crossing Points and must create legal and safe pathways to Europe. Lastly, there are numerous recommendations on the conditions and infrastructures at the reception centers and indicatively, to address the COVID-19 situation, the decongestion of the centres is supported, while the access to water and health services and information in reception centres are crucial. An interesting measure was the granting of residency status in Portugal to ensure access to healthcare under COVID-19 conditions.

Table 9 summarizes the findings of 11 entries, mostly policies and legal recommendations stemming from governmental and policy making bodies as well as civil society and NGOs.

Table 9. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools on the protection of human rights of migrants and against other threats related to them in the host country

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
<p>EU Member States sharing the responsibility for hosting migrants and refugees</p> <p>Financial cost of receiving refugees funded by the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund (AMIF) set up for the 2014-2020</p>	<p>Co-responsibility of EU MS for hosting migrants and refugees</p>	<p>The threats that stem from the overcrowding in the Greek islands can be tackled by European countries (Finland, France, Portugal) taking refugees from camps and reception centers in Greece and moving them to these countries. Also, residents in the Greek islands to share the responsibility with those in the mainland of Greece.</p>
<p>Compliance of EU states and institutions and authorities with international human rights standards</p> <p>Reform of existing migration policies and laws</p>	<p>EU MS and institutions compliance with international refugee law and international human rights law and the responsibilities stemming from it (search and rescue at sea, safe disembarkation and</p>	<p>Compliance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - States to ensure rescue at sea without discrimination, effective access to borders to seek protection, with no pushbacks or returns to countries where people could be at grave risk to their life and safety - Training of law enforcement officials, judges, and prosecutors

	<p>safe relocation, no pushbacks or returns to not safe countries, training of LEAs, compliance with UN Smuggling Protocol to combat misuse of laws for punishing human rights defenders)</p> <p>EU MS and institutions reform of migration policies, authorities' practices and legislation (revision of national laws on criminalisation of human rights defenders, opening of safe pathways to Europe, revision of limits of freedom of movement of refugees within EU, proportionate distribution of responsibilities among MS instead of state of first entry)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate number of vessels with search and rescue to be deployed along the routes taken by boats carrying refugees and migrants - European states building and participation in temporary arrangements to ensure predictable and prompt disembarkation and relocation of people rescued at sea - Refrain from policies that expand the use of detention for refugees and migrants, sanction secondary movements within the EU, and outsource border control responsibilities to countries outside Europe - Compliance of national laws on irregular entry, transit and stay and of the Facilitators' Package with the UN Smuggling Protocol as to the activities that should and should not be criminalized, and so as the laws are not misused to target human rights defenders engaging in acts of solidarity towards asylum seekers <p><u>Reform measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment of mechanism, by overhauling the present EU asylum rules, which assign disproportionate responsibility to the state of first entry, in order to provide for relocation arrangements, which prioritise family reunification and other connections to a particular EU or associated country and common European asylum determination and reception rules to achieve fairer and equivalent protection standards. - Revising EU legislation limiting freedom of movement of successful asylum-seekers within the EU and establishing a system of mutual recognition of positive decisions on international protection - Collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative national data concerning smuggling and/or related offences, with a view to facilitating a legislative reform that effectively prevent baseless prosecutions against human rights defenders-Open safe and legal routes into Europe, by offering a meaningful number of places for resettlement and alternative pathways to protection for refugees currently stranded
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		<p>in Libya, Turkey and neighbouring countries;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviewing migration policies at national and EU level to facilitate regular pathways for would-be migrants, including by reducing legal and administrative barriers to family reunification. - Other state-focused measures
Granting of residency status to all asylum seekers during COVID-19 situation	Access to healthcare, welfare, bank accounts during COVID-19 situation	COVID-19 as a threat, Portugal has announced that all asylum seekers and migrants who have applied for residency will automatically be granted residency status. It gives them access to healthcare, welfare, bank accounts, and more during coronavirus. The UN suggests that countries shall follow Portugal's example
Policies responding to COVID-19 in reception centres: Decongestion, access to water and health services and information in reception centres	COVID-19 policies in the reception centres	COVID-19 and overcrowding as a threat; Decongestion of hotspots due to COVID-19 threat, measures to ensure they have access to water and health services, information to migrants and asylum seekers on COVID-19 symptoms, Ensure that there is enough and adequate ;medical and nursing staff, as well as mental health support services in the reception centres
Change of legislation for fair distribution of responsibility among EU MS, and for sharing of responsibility among islands and mainland and for ensuring legal routes to Europe	Distribution of responsibilities and ensuring legal routes	<p>To address threats in reception centres and threats to the host country due to the lack of resources/infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Revision of the Dublin Treaty and establishment of a mandatory mechanism for responsibilities among all EU Member States. -Removing the geographical constraint on the Greek islands, and decent living conditions inland. -Ensuring safe and legal routes to Europe for people seeking asylum
Reform of migration policies: EU MS sharing responsibility for asylum seekers (financial support and safe pathways) with countries of first entry ; Greece and Bulgaria to ensure access to their territory; avoidance of use of force by Border	Cooperation among EU MS; practical assistance to EU MS countries of asylum seekers arrival; avoidance of use of force by BGs; safe pathways; safe BCPs;	To address the threat of death /safety and security and integrity of third country nationals arriving in Europe; EU member states sharing responsibility for asylum seekers arriving in Turkey, both through financial support and ensuring safe pathways to Europe. Greece and Bulgaria must ensure access to their territory for people seeking protection and border guards should refrain from excessive use of force against those gathered at the border. They must be allowed to enter through official border crossings, regardless of whether they have valid travel documents. Countries with external EU borders should keep sufficient,

Guards; External EU borders countries to keep sufficient, secure, appropriately located BCPs ; support to Greece and Bulgaria by EC and EU to reception and asylum procedures		appropriately located, and secure border crossing points open for refugees. The European Commission must also urgently coordinate any support that might be required to Greece and Bulgaria to ensure asylum seekers have access to adequate reception and asylum procedures. European member states should have their fair share of responsibility.
Sectoral / regional meetings at least every two years, Relaunch of Mesa Africa organisation; Creation of an interministerial commission for Africa coordinated by the ministry of foreign affairs. Annual monitoring reports.	Cooperation among Spain and African countries for distribution of responsibilities and ensuring legal routes	The long-term plan has been initiated to consolidate the relation between Spain and the African countries and collaborate in the regulation of migratory flows, to work on development cooperation. The policy is supported by the Spanish government, the European Union, and the United Nations.

4.7 Story Sharing on behalf of migrants and reintegration activities (tackling more than one of the abovementioned threats)

As stated previously, good practices, measures and tools that address more than one of the previously mentioned issues can be found listed under this general category. These 22 entries include mostly story sharing online platforms, where migrants and refugees share their own experiences during their migration journey to Europe and particularly to certain destination/host countries, raising in that way awareness for potential future migrants on the reality they encountered during their migration journey and inside the reception country, including the threats they faced and their integration and acceptance by the local society. Table 10 includes a brief description of these practices, that are directly linked to the perception of migrants and refugees towards the EU and the way they can be altered or influenced towards a more accurate depiction.

Table 10. List of identified good practices, measures, and tools that include story sharing from migrants and tackle more than one of the issues mentioned previously

Good Practice, Measure, Tool	Main topic addressed	Brief Description
Website with migrant stories	Raise awareness about the dangerous journey across the desert and the Mediterranean (deaths, smuggling etc.), about irregular migration, provide information on Europe, on socio-economic opportunities and	Aware Migrants is a project realized by the International Organization for Migration - IOM, with the technical and creative support of Horace communication agency and financed by the Italian Ministry of Interior, Department of Civil Liberties, and Immigration. It has created a dynamic webpage aiming to raise awareness on irregular migration along the main routes

	alternatives to migration at home.	from East/Western Africa across the desert and the Mediterranean. Works in Senegal, Ghana, and Niger. To do this, it disseminates contents adopting innovative tools and a community-based approach through migrant stories in order to help potential migrants make informed decisions by warning about dangers of the journey and realities of Europe, inform public opinion in countries of origin, transit and destination of conditions of migrants, to raise awareness of migration crisis as humanitarian emergency, support community stabilisation in countries of origin and promote information about alternatives e.g. socio-economic opportunities at home and give voice to returned migrants who can become communication agents and help potential migrants understand realities
Platform with collective information in different languages: English, Arabic, French and Farsi.	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe (risks, and integration)	w2eu.info provides information to refugees and migrants that might be useful on their journey to and through Europe. The site is divided into sections that range between different topics: an overview of each European country, information regarding medical assistance, information on migration policies and the Dublin III Regulation in each member state, information about systems such as "Alarmphone", contacts and addresses of organisations that work with assistance for refugees and other information related with asylum, detention, family and work, as well as awareness raising around the risks of the migration journey.
Mobile Application to access readily available information and services relevant to the migration process	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe (tackle risks, misinformation, false narratives and ensure integration)	MigAPP is an App developed by IOM to support migrants before they leave their country, during the journey and on arrival. MigApp offers a central and user friendly, one-stop-shop application where migrants can log on to using their mobile phones to access readily available information and services relevant to their specific migration process. Migrants can download for free on their mobile devices and which will aim and address the following needs: to help migrants make informed decisions throughout their migration process. Irregular and unsafe migration often is a result of lack of awareness about the risks involved in the process, ill-informed knowledge of visa and travel regulations, limited or non-existent interaction with legitimate service providers,

		and the absence of a balanced and unified platform for reliable and updated migration information and services. MigApp aims to offset the volume of misinformation on migration in circulation today, to provide migrants with access to services related to their migration process, to make some of IOM's programmes and services directly available to a wider group of migrants and to provide a platform for migrants to share their experiences, tell their story and upload a picture that will be shared among other MigApp users.
Peer-to-peer meetings in village halls, with film screenings, discussions and activities between past migrants and potential future migrants	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	Intervention is called Migrants as Messengers (MaM). It took place in Senegal, Guinea and Nigeria from 2017-2019, and involved returning migrants working as volunteers to share their stories and information about migration to Europe with those wanting to migrate, to help correct false ideas of Europe and life there. It used a peer-to-peer 'bottom-up' approach based on emotional identification between volunteers (ex-migrants) and potential migrants. The intervention resulted in: participants being 20% less likely to migrate than others in a control group; participants feeling 25 more aware of the real risks involved in irregular migration compared to the control group; and feeling 19 more informed about the risks and opportunities associated with migration in general.
Art exhibition and workshops	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	The International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the International Centre for Culture and Arts present a contemporary art exhibition is part of an IOM Tunisia initiative to present art merged with migration as a pluralistic phenomenon. A workshop for students of fine arts and young artists also took place during the residency to create a space for reflection and debate on the place of migration in art on the one hand, as well as to offer aspiring artists an opportunity to work alongside internationally recognized professional artists.
TV Report	TV Report on migrant women contribution	Broadcasted in 2015 as part of the Moroccan TV program « Des histoires et des Hommes » ["Stories and Men"] from the Moroccan TV channel "2M ". This report directed by Raja Saddiki highlights the positive contribution of

		migrant women by giving the floor to a community of Senegalese women who opened a restaurant in Casablanca.
Social and legal assistance at the leaving stage, cooperation activities with the local partners in the country of origin for migrant re-integration	Migrant reintegration from Italy to their country of origin	The Assisted Voluntary Return & Reintegration (AVRR) project is implemented by the Ministry of the Interior, Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration and implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and funded by the European Commission with the Asylum, Migration and Integration Funds (AMIF) Emergency , is aimed at irregular migrants present in Italy and characterized by fragility and social exclusion. Often for migrants and refugees, the risk of not finding what they were looking for is growing in the world and in Italy. For many, unemployment, illegal immigration, or exploitation remain a better alternative to the realities they have decided to leave. For others, no. The many disillusioned, trafficked or simply exhausted who would like to retrace their steps, however, often find themselves paralyzed by their illegal status or lack of resources to go home. The AVRIT project is aimed at these people. Upon return, most of the beneficiary undertook, supported by the IOM offices based in the various countries of origin, entrepreneurial activities in particular in commerce, transport, and breeding.
Information Points, information, and training sessions, dedicated free number on the RVA & R measure available in the main languages; operational-training manual on the measurement of RVA & R, Creation of a mapping of relevant associations and institutions	Migrant reintegration from Italy to their country of origin	The RE.VITA project ("Rete Ritorno Volontario Italia") intends to promote access to Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (RVA & R) of citizens of Third Countries present in Italy, through the dissemination of knowledge of RVA & R measures and active programs between potential beneficiaries, both final (migrants) and intermediate (public and private bodies operating in the migration sector). The intervention is therefore aimed at the activation and development of a network which includes the involvement of all the public and private actors who, in various ways and at different levels, work together in order to spread awareness of assisted voluntary return option. The project RE. VITA is co-financed by the Asylum Migration and Integration Fund 2014-2020 and the Italian Ministry of the Interior -

		Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration, implemented by IOM
Exhibition of a photographic project composed of 200 images and a series of short documentaries;	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	People of Tamba and Senegal/Sicily are two projects born thanks to The Josef and Anni Albers Foundation and Le Korsa, with the common goal of telling the story of migration. People of Tamba is a photographic project composed of 200 images that create a typological catalogue of society in Tambacounda, the most remote and rural region of Senegal, from which the majority of Senegalese migrants in Italy originate. Senegal/Sicily is a series of short documentaries created to bring to the Senegalese youth, among whom there are those who would like to leave, a sincere account of the risks involved in the journey and of what to expect in Europe.
Online Platform providing a collection of authentic stories, told by migrants and refugees themselves.	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	Telling the Real Story is a community-based platform disseminating stories about the extraordinary journeys made by Eritrean and Somali refugees and asylum seekers to Europe. Through these testimonies, those who might choose to embark on the journey are informed of the full scope and perils they may encounter in order to help them make an informed decision and prepare them for their future movements. The purpose of the Telling the Real Story platform is to allow Eritreans, Nigerians and Somalis who have made the journey to Europe to share their stories about the journey and the situation in destination countries. Telling the Real Story does not attempt to address the reasons for people's departure from their country of origin, but instead focuses on their experiences along the journey and in Europe. While some testimony givers talk about the reasons for their flight, many have chosen not to discuss their motives due to fear of reprisals that may affect relatives who have been left behind. Through the platform, made possible by the financial support from the European Commission, UNHCR is supporting brave Eritrean, Nigerian, and Somali survivors to tell their stories in their own words and to everyone who is willing to listen.

<p>Collective paper of migrant/refugee's story sharing</p>	<p>Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe</p>	<p>"From the Refugees' Perspective" is an attempt to provide a systematic analysis of the discourse among the persons of concern for the first time. From March to December 2016, a small team of researchers in UNHCR's Communicating with Communities Unit monitored refugee and migration related exchanges among Arabic speakers and Afghans on social media and issued weekly reports which are summarized in this document, providing a longitudinal view of 10 months of observation. In this study, refugees, and asylum-seekers – usually the disempowered objects of asylum policy – are turned into individuals who have something to say for themselves and whose voices are heard. The topics cover the refugees and migrants' decision-making processes and the interaction with smugglers prior to departure and all the way to the difficulties of reception and possibly integration in Europe. The paper provides the reader with a better understanding of mixed migration flows, the practices of smugglers and traffickers, the situations refugees and migrants have to cope with, their needs – including information needs – and their emotions.</p>
<p>YouTube videos for sharing experiences among migrants</p>	<p>Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe</p>	<p>'Odysseus 2.0' is a project which shows the main route of migration from West Africa to Europe, presented through the eyes of migrants going to Libya and Europe from various African countries</p>
<p>YouTube videos for sharing experiences of a refugee life</p>	<p>Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe</p>	<p>Run by YouTube Creators for Change and the International Rescue Committee (IRC), #MoreThanARefugee was launched in 2017 to coincide with World Refugee Day. This partnership sent seven YouTube Creators to five different countries – Jordan, Serbia, Uganda, Greece, and the United States – so that they could meet refugees, get to know them, and help share their stories. The main goal of this was to humanise refugees amidst the harmful narratives perpetuated during the refugee crisis. The project's official YouTube Blog highlights the experience of the filmmakers who, despite living in immensely different situations, discovered a sense of commonality and shared humanity with the refugees they met and interviewed.</p>

Reportage	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	<p>“Storie interRotte” is a report, divided into 4 episodes, two set in Africa and two in Val Susa on the border with France, is the work of two journalists, Andrea De Georgio and Annalisa Camilli and is part of the “Check point: stories of borders between Europe and Sahel”. The first episode of Inter-Stories leads us to Kayes, a rural area of Mali from which the majority of Malian migrants to Europe come. The second episode, set in the village of Sambacanou, tells the phenomenon of migrant remittances and the effects on the lives of those who remained. The third episode takes us right to the border with France. The fourth and last episode tells us about the widespread reception model that was created in 2016 in Val Susa on the border with France. This reportage interrogates the public, tells stories and people; for this reason, it is also projected in schools. The report aims to tell the foreigner as a person, with a name, a story and above all with the possibility of making himself known over time.</p>
Education days and training	Raise awareness before during and after the journey of migrants to Europe	<p>Education days for Moroccan youth wanting to migrate, with the idea of "education days as a tool for social change". In the education days the organisation shares the experience of young Moroccan migrants in Spain, information about the existing legal system in Spain, and the problems of integration aspiring migrants will face if they decide to go to Europe in general.</p>
Website	Raise awareness on the migrant journeys and the dangers they face on a daily basis	<p>TRACKS is a website, that collects migrant and refugees' extraordinary stories of survival, hope and home. TRACKS began with a focus on Syrians becoming soon a worldwide initiative.</p>
Trainings, regional job fairs, website.	Migrant reintegration from Germany to their country of origin	<p>Migration for development programme is a project the objective of which is the prospects for economic and social participation in selected countries of origin are improved for returning migrants, the local population, and internally displaced persons. The programme has been creating better opportunities for a fresh start for these people in selected countries of origin since the beginning of 2017. For example, a migration advice centre was opened in Tunis in March 2017 where Tunisians can obtain</p>

		<p>advice regarding the opportunities available in the German and Tunisian labour markets. In order to provide those interested in returning with the appropriate information while they are still in Germany, all the essential information on advisory services and prospects in the countries of origin can be found on the Startfinder website and is tailored to the specific target group. The programme is also working closely with towns and communities in Germany.</p>
Trainings and supporting methods	Migrant reintegration from Germany to their country of origin	<p>The Federal Ministry for Cooperation and Development launched a program called “Perspective Home” aimed at migrants who do not qualify for residency or protection in Germany, or those who choose to voluntarily return. ““Perspective Home” has had a significant impact in creating jobs or setting up companies and more than 57,000 opportunities were created as a result. The program has also supported more than 11,000 small and medium companies in countries of origin through securing or creating jobs for returnees. It is estimated that, on average, 5 family members are supported through each job placement.</p>
Study on art-based initiatives	Address the way potential migrants in Algeria and Tunisia see Europe	<p>Combining digital humanities, cultural studies and migration studies, the study “Hope and disillusion. The Depiction of Europe in Algerian and Tunisian Cultural Productions about Undocumented Migration”, analyses the depiction of Europe in Algerian and Tunisian cultural productions about undocumented migration.</p>
Training sessions	Counteract against asylum seekers' 'misperceptions' about 'values and standards' in Belgium, particularly regarding gender.	<p>Trainings on gender equality and against sexual harassment for Afghan men and women (15 years and older) organized by the Humanitarian Welfare Association. These trainings were developed in the framework of a small-scale project funded by Fedasil to meet one of the three present priorities, i.e. 'strengthen the knowledge of applicants for international protection on values and standards in Belgian society.' Thus, these trainings can be considered as measures to combat 'misperceptions' asylum seekers have about 'values and standards' in Belgium, particularly regarding gender.</p>

5 Conclusions and the way forward

This deliverable managed with the support of the consortium to identify and sort and briefly analyse the distinct good practices, which are either completed or ongoing. It also provides a broad picture of the current (2015-today) good practices that have been implemented across a global scale and can be utilized by consortium partners at the EU level. To collect the good practices, both a direct and indirect approach on addressing or counteracting against migrants' misperceptions was adopted. There are several examples of the collected entries which have no direct link with false narratives, although the proposed countermeasure affects, among others, the perception that migrants have about Europe.

This collection of good practices also provided the opportunity to reflect upon and deeply understand several possible solutions and approaches that have or could be implemented to effectively tackle the issue of inaccurate expectations and problematic narratives, which influence migration aspirations that may lead to several problems related to the migrant and/or the country of destination including security threats and risks. It can also showcase that a good practice may address a threat which was accurately perceived by migrants and refugees; the majority of good practices were dedicated to addressing a specific threat posed either to host countries/borders or to migrants themselves.

In general, evaluation schemes are required to measure the impact and the effectiveness of the implemented counteractions. As also indicated within deliverable D2.2, the lack of viable countermeasures and toolkits, along with the insufficient data relating to evaluation methods that were used to rate the countermeasures, limit the potential of research to perceive the exact impact that the countermeasure may have on the affected groups (migrants, natives, etc.). This has led the consortium to further analyse the collected data, by sharing with the relevant consortium partners a new spreadsheet which will be developed following similar approach as EWSI's (European Web Site on Integration) and will synthesise all the information needed to judge whether the practice is efficient and adaptable to other contexts. This spreadsheet will include several categories including general threats, specified and distinct threats as well as proposed good practices to tackle each threat. To determine the most effective good practices, an evaluation scheme will be developed within WP5, in which the eligibility and selection criteria will be set to rank and evaluate each good practice. Additionally, the Consortium will conduct interviews with migrants, Civil Society Organisations, policymakers, LEAs, and other stakeholders under WP3, which can shed light on their perspectives, understanding and ranking of 'best practices'.

However it is worth mentioning that, when comparing implemented countermeasures among countries -at national and international level-, 'similar' good practices had different impact on migrants and general public due to several factors which possibly affect the level of efficiency of the provided countermeasures, such as cultural differences, historical, socio-economic background and the general country context. raises interesting tracks in the area of research and could be further explored.

To conclude, the collection of the aforementioned good practices could be utilised as an initial library of knowledge, as far as it concerns the best ways to prevent or counter-act migration issues or threats derived from false narratives. Considering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set on the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, this library would be a helpful asset on the one hand, by implementing preliminary countermeasures to tackle false narratives and to inform migrants on the high-risk travel to Europe and on the other hand, these could be used as lessons learnt in terms of

preparedness, planning and implementation of similar measures to resolve or prevent a humanitarian crisis in the host country.

Bearing in mind the COVID-19 situation in different countries and the few inputs collected from this document, it is of utmost importance to gather, study and analyse the relation between this unpredictable situation and (mis)perceptions among asylum seekers, refugees and migrants towards Europe, but most importantly best practices to counter that threat in the migration and security context. The findings related to COVID-19 and its consequences will be further elaborated and analysed under the task T5.3 *“Create a library of identified threats and derive individual counter strategies and describe good practices to be distributed via a user-validated good practice library”*.

Beyond the scope of this deliverable, good practices tackling threats linked with such narratives should be continuously investigated and monitored to prevent and counter, where possible, potential new ways of false narratives distribution.

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Other applicable documents

PERCEPTIONS Deliverable D2.2 Secondary analysis of studies, projects, and narratives (30th of January 2020)

PERCEPTIONS Deliverable D2.3 Analysis of policies, policy recommendations and legal frameworks (31st of March 2020)

PERCEPTIONS Deliverable D2.4 Collection of threats and security issues (31st of March 2020)